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Microalgae strain catalogue

A strain selection guide for microalgae users: cultivation and chemical characteristics for high added-value products

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4th Edition

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Microalgae strain catalogue - A strain selection guide for microalgae users: 4th edition

University of Manchester, Manchester, UK
EnhanceMicroAlgae 2023

The 4th edition of this catalogue contains information on the cultivation and composition characteristics of 50 microalgae. Each entry includes relevant links to Atlantic Area stakeholders known to have a relevant connection with each of the species listed, be it in the form of culture collections, research expertise, technology developers, or biomass producers. We invite the readers to visit and/or join the EnhanceMicroAlgae [Stakeholder database](#): an easily accessible, visual and open access database that brings together all the European Atlantic Area players working in the microalgae sector.

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Microalgae production for high added value compounds is identified as a business sector with high growth potential in the coming decades, especially in the Atlantic Area. Barriers to improve an industrial use are dominated by a lack of technology expertise.

*The **EnhanceMicroAlgae** project aims to stimulate research, innovation, industrial development and transnational cooperation within the Atlantic area microalgae sector. The main objective is to contribute to the competitiveness of microalgal-based industries in the Atlantic Area.*

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CONTENTS

Introduction	7
Important notes	8
Chlorophyta (Green Algae)	9
Class: Chlorophyceae.....	10
1. <i>Ankistrodesmus falcatus</i>	10
2. <i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	12
3. <i>Chromochloris zofingiensis</i>	15
4. <i>Desmodesmus subspicatus</i>	17
5. <i>Dunaliella salina</i>	20
6. <i>Dunaliella tertiolecta</i>	25
7. <i>Graesiella sp.</i>	28
8. <i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	30
9. <i>Scenedesmus obliquus</i>	34
10. <i>Scenedesmus quadricauda</i>	38
11. <i>Selenastrum capricornutum</i>	41
Class: Trebouxiophyceae	43
12. <i>Auxenochlorella protothecoides</i>	43
13. <i>Botryococcus braunii</i>	45
14. <i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i>	47
15. <i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	50
16. <i>Jaagichlorella luteoviridis</i>	56
17. <i>Parachlorella kessleri</i>	58
18. <i>Picochlorum sp.</i>	61
Class: Chlorodendrophyceae	63
19. <i>Tetraselmis subcordiformis</i>	63
20. <i>Tetraselmis suecica</i>	67
Bacillariophyta (Diatoms)	71
Class: Mediophyceae (pennate diatoms)	72
21. <i>Chaetoceros calcitrans</i>	72
22. <i>Cyclotella sp.</i>	76

23.	<i>Odontella aurita</i>	78
24.	<i>Skeletonema sp.</i>	81
25.	<i>Thalassiosira pseudonana</i>	84
Class: Bacillariophyceae (centric diatoms)		87
26.	<i>Navicula sp.</i>	87
27.	<i>Nitzschia sp.</i>	90
28.	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	94
Ochrophyta (Ochrophytes)		99
Class: Chrysophyceae		100
29.	<i>Ochromonas sp.</i>	100
Class: Eustigmatophyceae		102
30.	<i>Microchloropsis salina</i>	102
31.	<i>Nannochloropsis oculata</i>	105
Euglenophyta (Euglenoids)		109
Class: Euglenophyceae		110
32.	<i>Euglena gracilis</i>	110
Cryptophyta (Cryptomonads)		112
Class: Cryptophyceae		113
33.	<i>Rhodomonas sp.</i>	113
Haptophyta (Haptophytes)		120
Class: Coccolithophyceae		121
34.	<i>Isochrysis galbana</i>	121
35.	<i>Tisochrysis lutea</i>	125
Class: Pavlovophyceae.....		128
36.	<i>Pavlova sp.</i>	128
Dinophyta (Dinoflagellates)		131
Class: Dinophyceae.....		132
37.	<i>Amphidinium carterae</i>	132
38.	<i>Alexandrium minutum</i>	135
39.	<i>Cryptocodinium cohnii</i>	138
40.	<i>Karlodinium veneficum</i>	140
Rhodophyta (Red algae)		143

Class: Cyanidiophyceae	144
41. <i>Galdieria sulphuraria</i>	144
Class: Porphyridiophyceae	146
42. <i>Porphyridium purpureum</i>	146
Class: Rhodellophyceae	150
43. <i>Rhodella</i> sp.	150
Cyanobacteria (Blue-green algae)	154
Class: Cyanophyceae	155
44. <i>Anabaena cylindrica</i>	155
45. <i>Arthrospira platensis</i>	158
46. <i>Lyngbya lutea</i>	163
47. <i>Microcystis aeruginosa</i>	165
48. <i>Nostoc</i> sp.	167
49. <i>Synechococcus</i> sp.	170
50. <i>Synechocystis</i> sp.	173
Appendix 1. Media recipes	176
A.1. Artificial Seawater (ASW) medium	177
A.2. Blue-Green medium (BG11).....	178
A.3. Bold's Basal Medium (BBM) and 3N-BBM.....	179
A.4. Chu 13 medium (Modified).....	181
A.5. Conway medium.....	182
A.6. Detmer medium (DM) modified	183
A.7. f/2 medium.....	184
A.8. f/2+Si (Guillard's medium for diatoms)	185
A.9. Jaworski's Medium (JM).....	186
A.10. Kuhl medium	187
A.11. SOT medium	188
A.12. Sueoka medium.....	189
A.13. Walne's medium.....	190
A.14. Zarrouk medium.....	191
A.15. Modified K medium	192
A.16. ES-DK medium	193

A.17. GSe medium (modified GPM medium)	194
A.18. L1 basal culture medium	195
A.19. ESAW H1 medium.....	196
A.20. L1 medium.....	197
A.21. Daigo's IMK medium	198
A.22. LDM medium	199
A.23. A+ medium	200
Appendix 2. Culture collections	203
Appendix 3. List of images	204
References	208

Introduction

Microalgae are a broad group of diverse microorganisms that are typically single-celled, photosynthetic organisms that derive from marine, brackish, freshwater or terrestrial environments. In this catalogue we include both eukaryotic and prokaryotic (cyanobacteria) species.

There is increasing commercial interest in the usage of microalgae for a wide variety of applications including animal feed, aquaculture, biofertiliser, waste pollutant remediation, sources of nutrients and chemicals for food production, nutraceutical supplements such as omega-3 fatty acids, cosmetics, biofuels and bioenergy, pharmaceutical products, colourings, antioxidants, flavourings, and other uses. These applications all depend on the characteristics and chemical composition of different microalgae species and strains.

It is estimated that there are many thousands of microalgae species with many different properties. In addition, strains of microalgae belonging to the same species or closely related species will have different characteristics and will have differences in their chemical composition due to living in different environments and adapting to the different physical conditions of that environment. Of these many possible strains, only a relatively small number have been collected and are stored within individual labs and in culture collections. Only a small number of strains of different species have been physiologically and biochemically characterised, and an even smaller number of strains are currently commercially used.

While the majority of available microalgae strains remain largely uncharacterised, a substantial amount of research has been performed on a small number of strains with desirable characteristics. However, strain characteristic information can be challenging to identify and is typically found within many different, sometime inaccessible literature sources. Therefore this resource has been developed in order to provide collated information on the cultivation characteristics and chemical composition of selected microalgae species.

Each entry summarises the characteristics of a different species, with details taken from one or more strains of that species, which are present in a publically accessible culture collection. As much details as possible about the cultivation procedures of the strains have been described so that the chemical composition characteristics might be reproducible. However, it must be noted, that strain properties can vary based on different environmental parameters and even between different locations where conditions are considered identical. Moreover, originally identical strains (from the same original source) can adapt their characteristics over time, therefore some caution must be taken when interpreting information assigned to a particular named strain.

We hope that you find this catalogue resource useful and informative. In addition, any feedback to this resource is welcome.

The EnhanceMicroAlgae team

Important notes

- The names of the microalgae species presented within this catalogue are in accordance with their currently accepted taxonomic status at the time of publication. However, names are subject to change as a result of new taxonomic discoveries. The reader is encouraged to refer to [AlgaeBase](https://www.algaebase.org/) for the most updated names and classification of microalgae.
- Unless otherwise specified, it should be interpreted that cultivation data shown in the following pages was obtained during cultivation in batch operation and in phototrophic growth mode (using either air or artificial supplementation of CO₂).
- A compilation of important algal growth media recipes shown throughout the catalogue is included in Appendix 1.
- Similarly, a (non-exhaustive) list of major Culture Collections is provided in Appendix 2.

A list of common acronyms used throughout the catalogue is presented below:

Acronym	Description
PBR	Photobioreactor
nd	Non-disclosed
STR	Stirred Tank Reactor
L:D	Light:Dark cycle (photoperiod)
BG11	Blue-Green medium
BBM	Bold's Basal Medium

Definitions:

- Lux (lx): A measure of radiant light from a standard candle that falls on one square meter of surface area one meter from the source.
- Micromol ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$): One micromol per square meter per second. A unit of measure of the amount of light hitting a surface that is in the range of 400-700 nanometers.
- Watts (W): Watts per square meter (W/m^2). A unit of measure of the amount of light energy hitting a surface that is in the range of 400-800 nanometers.

Chlorophyta (Green Algae)

The Chlorophyta comprises most green algae, with four major lineages forming the crown group: the classes Chlorophyceae, Trebouxiophyceae, Chlorodendrophyceae and Ulvophyceae. Members of Chlorophyceae are mostly unicellular or colonial flagellates that thrive in freshwater or terrestrial environments, and contain many green algae commonly used for biotechnological purposes ¹. Members of class Trebouxiophyceae are mostly coccoid unicells that thrive in drier habitats, while Ulvophyceae members are predominantly marine. The class Chlorodendrophyceae contains other green flagellates, and is mainly represented by species of *Tetraselmis* ¹.

Major classes

No. of species in Algaebase

Chlorophyceae	3830
Trebouxiophyceae	938
Chlorodendrophyceae	62
Ulvophyceae	2741
Pyramimonadophyceae	15

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above.

Class: Chlorophyceae

1. *Ankistrodesmus falcatus*

A fast-growing freshwater microalga. It is considered an important source of lipids and pigments, and it can also accumulate a relatively high protein content ².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCNM-1031, KJ671624, CMSACR1001

1.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ³	<p>System: 500 mL conical flasks</p> <p>Medium: BG-11, BBM, Chu-10, Zarrouk</p> <p>Temperature: 25 ± 2°C</p> <p>Light: 12h L: 12h D, at 30, 60 and 150 μmol/m²/s; 12h L: 12h D, 18h L: 6h D, 6h L: 18h D, 24h L:0h D and 0h L: 24h D at 60 μmol/m²/s</p>	nd	6.14 mg/L/day (with BG-11 and Chu-10 media)	210.4 mg/L (with Zarrouk's medium)
nd ²	<p>System: airlift photobioreactor</p> <p>Medium: BG-11</p> <p>Temperature: below 30°C in batch and 36°C in continuous cultivation</p> <p>Carbon source: CO₂</p> <p>Light: 170 μmol/m²/s in batch and 185 μmol/m²/s in continuous cultivation, L:D cycle nd</p>	nd	nd	1.04 (under batch cultivation) 1.56 (under continuous cultivation)

CMSACR1001 ⁴	System: 1 L conical flask Medium: BG-11 Temperature: 25 ± 1 °C Light: 60 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.035 (under phytohormones supplementation)	0.431 (under phytohormones supplementation)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

1.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
16.23 – 57.70% lipids ² --- 35% lipids ⁴ 43% carbohydrates 17.5% proteins	nd	17.89 µg/mL total ⁴ chlorophyll 2.65 µg/mL total carotenoids	C12:0 0.15-1.96% ² C14:0 0.36-0.93% C16:0 28.87-40.66% C16:1 0.25-1.28% C18:0 3.93-6.38% C18:1 20.84-33.48% C18:2 8.01-18.90% C18:3(6) 0.19-0.97% C18:3(3) 3.30-18.70% C18:4 1.14-4.91% C24:0 0.06-3.50%

1.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. falcatus* CCAP 202/14A, 202/14B, 202/14C, 202/15C, 202/5C
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Ankistrodesmus* sp. BEA 0536B, 1117B, 0742B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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2. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*

A photosynthetic biflagellate microalga (Chlorophyta) that has been studied for more than 30 years as a model for basic and applied physiology and biochemistry, partly due to its ease of culturing and the ability to manipulate its genetics⁵. It can be cultivated photoautotrophically and also heterotrophically or mixotrophically⁶. Commercially, it is of interest for producing biopharmaceuticals and biofuel, as well being a valuable research tool in making hydrogen.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 90, CC-124, CC-125

2.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
UTEX 90 ⁷	System: Flat-vertical PBR Medium: minimal medium Carbon source: glacial acetic acid with supplemental CO ₂ Temperature: 25-28°C Light: outdoor light conditions during May to July 2003 in Dae-jeon, Korea.	nd	nd	1.45 (fresh) 12-18 (concentrated)
CC-124 ⁸ wild-type mt(-) 137c	System: flask on a rotatory shaker Medium: TAP medium Carbon source: acetic acid Temperature: 23 °C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~1.25x10 ⁷ cells/mL
CC-125 ⁸ wild-type mt(+) 137c	System: flask on a rotatory shaker Medium: TAP medium Carbon source: acetic acid Temperature: 23 °C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~1.10x10 ⁷ cells/mL

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

2.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
CC-124 ⁸ 16.8% lipid in Control 39.8% lipid in N-starvation 37.6% lipid in S-starvation	Autotrophic ⁹ 48.1% C 5.8% N 7.3% H 38.8% O		C14:0 0.8% ¹⁰ C16:0 24% C16:1 1.9% C16:2 1.2% C16:3 0.9% C18:0 5.2% C18:1 23.5% C18:2 15.4% C18:3 21.6% C20:4 0.5% C20:5 4.9% C22:0 0.2%
CC-125 14.2% lipid in Control 41.4% lipid in N-starvation 39.7% lipid in S-starvation	Mixotrophic 50.7% C 3.5% N 7.9% H 37.9% O	Autotrophic ⁹ 0.9% Chlorophyll-a 1.5% Chlorophyll-b	
--- Autotrophic ⁹ 26.1% protein 18.9% lipid 50.8% carbohydrate	Heterotrophic 50.5% C 10.5% N 7.7% H 31.3% O	Mixotrophic 0.7% Chlorophyll-a 1.3% Chlorophyll-b Heterotrophic 1.8% Chlorophyll-a 0.8% Chlorophyll-b	ΣSFA=30.2 ΣMUFA=25.4 ΣPUFA=44.5
Mixotrophic 30.3% protein 27.9% lipid 38.1% carbohydrate			
Heterotrophic 22.2% protein 28.7% lipid 44.8% carbohydrate			

2.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. reinhardtii* 11/32A, 11/32B, 11/32C, 11/32CW15+, 11/45
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes¹¹:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*,

Phaeodactylum tricornutum, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp.,
Scenedesmus sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp.,
Thalassiosira weissflogii, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus*¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{13,14}, *Dunaliella salina*^{13,15,16}, *Micractinium inermum*¹³, *Chlorella vulgaris*^{17,18}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*^{19,20}, *Nannochloropsis salina*¹⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*²⁰

Location: Sheffield, UK

- **Name:** [Microalgae group at Centro de Investigaciones Científicas Avanzadas \(CICA\), University of A Coruña](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, genomics, monitoring. Research outputs involving microalgae at University of A Coruña include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*²¹, *Dunaliella salina*²², *Haematococcus pluvialis*²³

Location: A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [MicroSynbiotix](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Aquaculture, medical.

Aiming to reduce antibiotics use in farmed seafood, the company is researching how microalgae can be employed as a delivery transport of recombinant proteins to fish. P-o-C (proof-of-concept) research with *C. reinhardtii*²⁴.

Locations: Cork, Ireland and San Diego California, USA

- **Name:** [University of Manchester](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organization type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, molecular biology, engineering, mathematical models. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*²⁵⁻²⁸, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*²⁹, *Haematococcus pluvialis*³⁰, *T-isochrysis lutea*³¹, *Pseudanabaena catenata*³²

Location: Manchester, UK

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3. *Chromochloris zofingiensis*

Formerly known as *Chlorella zofingiensis* (Dönn) ³³. A freshwater green microalga. It can grow phototrophically, heterotrophically and mixotrophically, and it is easy to be cultured and scaled up both indoors and outdoors, achieving high cell density. It is considered a potential alternative for astaxanthin production ³⁴.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX B32

3.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ³⁵	System: 300 mL glass PBRs Medium: BG11 Carbon source: 5% CO ₂ Temperature: 25°C Light: 300 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	2.50
UTEX B32 ³⁶	System: Flat-panel, airlift-loop PBR Medium: Modified M8 Carbon source: CO ₂ Temperature: 25°C Light: from 63 to 245 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	0.75	12

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

3.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
nd	nd	2.4 mg/g astaxanthin ³⁶ 1.3 mg/g canthaxanthin 0.8 mg/g ketolutein	335 mg/g TAGs ³⁶

3.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. zofingiensis* CCAP 211/14, 211/51, 221/2
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

- **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. zofingiensis* BEA 0468B, 0496B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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4. *Desmodesmus subspicatus*

Formerly known as *Scenedesmus subspicatus* (Chodat)³³. A eukaryotic freshwater Chlorophyceae strain with applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically³⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 276/20

4.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 276/20 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.09	0.11	2.1
CCAP 276/20 ³⁹	System: 250 mL flasks (200 mL working volume) Medium: Jaworski's medium (different P levels) Temperature: 25°C Light: 144.8 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	nd	nd	2.4x10 ⁶ cells mL ⁻¹ <i>(in low-P medium)</i> 5.2x10 ⁶ cells mL ⁻¹ <i>(in intermediate-P medium)</i> 4.6x10 ⁶ cells mL ⁻¹ <i>(in high-P medium)</i>
nd ⁴⁰ <i>Isolated from the River Nile, Egypt</i>	System: 1 L flasks (700 mL working volume) Medium: BBM Temperature: 28±2°C Light: 2500 lux, L:D cycle nd	nd	~0.9 <i>(stationary phase)</i> ~0.65 <i>(late exponential phase)</i>	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

4.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
58% protein ³⁸ 16% lipid 29% carbohydrate	nd	19.6 mg/g total chlorophyll ³⁸ 0.3 mg/g total carotenoid --- 0.098±0.061 pg cell ⁻¹ Chlorophyll-a (<i>in Low N medium</i>) ⁴¹ 0.617±0.111 pg cell ⁻¹ Chlorophyll-a (<i>in High N medium</i>) ⁴¹	C14:0 1.5% ³⁸ C16:0 21.8% C16:1 6.0% C16:2 4.0% C16:3 0.7% C18:1 17.9% C18:2 21.7% C18:3 3.8% other 22.6%

4.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Desmodesmus* sp. (various), *D. subspicatus* BEA 0750B, 0141B, 0141/1, 0141/2, 0561, 0530B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, mathematical models, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus subspicatus* ¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* ^{13,14}, *Dunaliella salina* ¹³, *Micractinum inermum* ¹³, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{42,43}

Location: Swansea, UK
- Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)
Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus subspicatus* ¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* ^{13,14}, *Dunaliella salina* ^{13,15,16}, *Micractinum inermum* ¹³, *Chlorella vulgaris* ^{17,18}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ^{19,20}, *Nannochloropsis salina* ¹⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ²⁰

Location: Sheffield, UK

- **Name:** [Spanish Society of Microalgae and Subproducts](#) (SEMS)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development
Expertise: biotechnology, chemistry, marketing and valorisation. The company offers various laboratory services and products for agriculture, with various microalgae being produced on a continuous basis ⁴⁴:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Scenedesmus* sp., and ***Scenedesmus subspicatus***
- Locations:** Rota, Spain

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5. *Dunaliella salina*

A eukaryotic marine Chlorophyceae strain that is extremely salt - tolerant and is widely cultivated as a source of beta-carotene. It has commercial interest as a source of anti-oxidant, colouring, nutritional supplement and cosmetics ⁴⁵⁻⁴⁸. Large scale cultivation of *D. salina* is typically in open pond or large coastal lagoons ⁴⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 19/18

5.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 19/18 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: F2 (f/2) medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.135	0.224	1.28
CCAP 19/18 ⁵⁰	System: PBR Medium: sterilised seawater Temperature: 21°C Light: 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (blue light, red light) 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	~1.0 (red light) ~0.7 (blue light)
nd ⁵¹ <i>obtained from NLP corp (Busan, Korea)</i>	System: PBR (5L, 3 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 108.9 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.0375	0.25
nd ⁵² <i>obtained from Guangyu Co. (Shangai, China)</i>	System: Bubble column (350 mL working volume) Medium: high-salinity medium Temperature: 28°C Light: 100, 800 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous	0.66	nd	3.38 (at 800 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) ~0.5 (at 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

5.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
48% protein ³⁸ 24% lipid 23% carbohydrate ---	41% C ³⁸ 2% N C/N ratio 21	27 mg/g beta-carotene ³⁸	C16:0 28.1% ³⁸ C16:1 2.0% C18:0 2.9% C18:1 17.2% C18:2 9.2% C18:3 15.9% C20:1 4.8% other 19.9%
57% protein ⁵³ 6% lipid 32% carbohydrate ---			
~42% lipids in two-stage system ⁵⁴			

5.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. salina* 19/12, 19/18, 19/20, 19/25, 19/31, *Dunaliella* sp.
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. salina* IFDSAL-JY215, IFDSAL-DIOX, DSALGB1, DSALGC3
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. salina* BEA 0001, BEA 0162B, 0165B,
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, ***Dunaliella salina***, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp.,

Scenedesmus sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp.,
Thalassiosira weissflogii, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Location: Lisbon, Portugal

- **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, mathematical models, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus*¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{13,14}, ***Dunaliella salina***¹³,
*Micractinium inermum*¹³, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{42,43}

Location: Swansea, UK

- **Name:** [Algalimento](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of⁵⁵:

- *Tetraselmis* sp., *Spirulina canariensis*, ***Dunaliella salina***

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- **Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Environment, biotechnology. Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus*¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{13,14}, ***Dunaliella salina***^{13,15,16}, *Micractinium inermum*¹³, *Chlorella vulgaris*^{17,18}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*^{19,20}, *Nannochloropsis salina*¹⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*²⁰

Location: Sheffield, UK

- **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela

Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [***Dunaliella salina***, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*]⁵⁰, *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁵⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.]⁵⁷ *Rhodomonas lens*⁵⁸

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

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European Regional Development Fund

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- **Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Anabaena* sp.^{59,60}, *Porphyridium purpureum*⁶⁰, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*⁶⁰, *Nostoc*⁶⁰,
*Dunaliella salina*⁶¹

Location: Sevilla, Spain

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶²,
*Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶²,
*Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶²,
*Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium*
*baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, ***Dunaliella***
salina^{62,65}, ***Dunaliella*** sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶²,
*Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia*
sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶²,
Porphyridium purpureum (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶²,
Rhodomonas salina^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶²,
*Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶²,
*Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [Microalgae group at Centro de Investigaciones Científicas Avanzadas \(CICA\), University of A Coruña](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, genomics, monitoring. Research outputs involving microalgae at University of A Coruña include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*²¹, ***Dunaliella salina***²², *Haematococcus pluvialis*²³

Location: A Coruña, Spain

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Interreg
Atlantic Area
European Regional Development Fund

EUROPEAN UNION

- **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of Spirulina-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture ⁷². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from ⁷³:
 - *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana* ⁷³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.
Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - Spirulina, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

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6. *Dunaliella tertiolecta*

A eukaryotic brackish water Chlorophyceae strain that is less salt tolerant than *D. salina* and has lower productivity of beta-carotene but is of interest for its fatty acid yields with applications for nutritional supplements, and biofuel ⁷⁴.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 19/6B, BE 003

6.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 16/6B ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: F2 (f/2) medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.048	0.128	1.6
CCAP 19/6B ⁵⁰	System: PBR Medium: sterilised seawater Temperature: 21°C Light: 300 µmol/m ² /s (blue light, red light) 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	~1.2 (red light) ~0.8 (blue light)
nd ⁵¹ <i>obtained from NLP corp (Busan, Korea)</i>	System: PBR (5L, 3 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 108.9 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.0442	0.28
BE 003 ⁷⁵	System: PBR (2.2 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium (modified with various NaNO ₃ concentrations) Temperature: 28°C Light: 17.5 klx continuous	nd	nd	0.45±0.02 (75 mg/L NaNO ₃) 1.27±0.07 (300 mg/L NaNO ₃)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

6.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
58% protein ³⁸ 12% lipid 8% carbohydrate --- ~40% lipids in two-stage system ⁵¹	44% C ³⁸ 2% N C/N ratio 20	3.95±0.06 to 5.1±0.4 mg/g total carotenoids ⁷⁶	C16:0 17.7% ³⁸ C16:1 0.9% C16:2 3.0% C16:3 1.2% C16:4 10.6% C18:1 4.9% C18:2 12.4% C18:3 30.2% other 19.1%

6.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* AC148, *Dunaliella* sp. AC769
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* 19/22, 19/23, 19/24, 19/27, 19/42, 19/5, 19/6B, 19/7C
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* IFREMER (PLY83), *Dunaliella* sp.
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *D. tertiolecta* BEA 0837B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education
Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ⁵⁰, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁵⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.] ⁵⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ⁷⁷

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like*⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella sp.*⁶², ***Dunaliella tertiolecta***^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia sp.*⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum (Porphyridium cruentum)*^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxins \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.

Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, ***Dunaliella***, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

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7. *Graesiella* sp.

A unicellular green microalga with broadly ellipsoidal or globose cells. This microalga presents high capacity of adaptation to a wide range of culture pH ⁷⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
WBG-1, NC-M1

7.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
WBG-1 ⁷⁸	<p>System: bubbled column PBR, 10 L circular pond, 30 L tank PBR, 200 m² raceway pond</p> <p>Medium: modified BG11 medium</p> <p>Carbon source: 1% v/v CO₂</p> <p>Temperature: 30°C</p> <p>Light: 300 μmol/m²/s, L:D cycle nd</p>	nd	18.9 g/m ² /d (in 30L tank)	161.8 g/m ² (in 30L tank)
NC-M1 ⁷⁹	<p>System: 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks</p> <p>Medium: BG11 medium</p> <p>Temperature: 25°C</p> <p>Light: 50 μmol/m²/s, 16h L:8h D cycle</p>	nd	nd	1.2 (with 45.2 μM Fe)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

7.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
12-14% protein ⁷⁸ 32-40% carbohydrate 22-35% lipid (in 200 m ² raceway cultivation) --- 30-65% lipid ⁷⁹	nd	nd	C5-C14 5-10% ⁷⁸ C16-C18 70-75% C19-C24 7-10% --- C14:0 27.4-29.64% ⁷⁹ C16:0 0.83-5.49% C16:2 1.19-4.99% C18:1 27.43-47.04% C18:2 8.86-22.03% C20:2 6.72-13.52%

7.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *G. emersoni* CCAP 211/1A, 211/1M, 211/1N, 211/15, 211/55, 211/8G, 211/8H, 2118P
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *G. vacuolata* BEA 0618B, 0615B, 0573B, 0616B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

8. *Haematococcus pluvialis*

A eukaryotic freshwater Chlorophyceae strain with the ability to produce very high concentrations of astaxanthin, with applications for aquaculture, nutritional supplement, and cosmetics, and with antioxidant characteristics. *H. pluvialis* has a green phase then a red phase of growth, which is induced by light, nitrogen or saline stress^{80–82}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 34/6, SCCAP K-0084, SCCAP K-0084, LUGU, CPCC 93

8.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 34/6 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.098	0.157	3.14
SCCAP K-0084 ⁸³	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: BG11 medium Carbon source: ribose, sodium acetate, or gluconate Temperature: 25°C Light: 45±3 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	1.03 (on ribose) 0.77 (on acetate) 1.12 (on gluconate)
SCCAP K-0084 ⁸³	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: BG11 medium Carbon source: gluconate Temperature: 25°C Light: 105±3 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	2.09
LUGU ⁸⁴ (18S GenBankKM115647.1)	System: 1 L flask (650 mL working volume). Medium: BG11 medium + fulvic acid	nd	nd	1.57 (with 0 mg/L fulvic acid) 1.84

	Carbon source: sodium acetate Temperature: 25°C Light: 50 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ L:D cycle nd			(with 5 mg/L fulvic acid)
CPCC 93 ⁸⁵	System: 2.2 L PBR Medium: M1B5 Temperature: 23±2°C Light: 15-30 klx 12 h L: 12h D	nd	nd	2.028±0.09 (on air) 4.37±0.07 (on 5% CO ₂)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

8.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
68% protein ³⁸ 26% lipid 9% carbohydrate	36% C ³⁸ 4% N C/N ratio 10 --- 43.57±0.61% C ⁸⁵ 6.26±0.54% H 1.98±0.16% N 0.47±0.03% S	23.2 mg/g astaxanthin ³⁸ 2.8 mg/g beta-carotene 10.2 mg/g lutein 5.8 mg/g total chlorophyll (in red phase) --- 5.2±1.7 ug/mL chlorophyll ⁸³ (at 0 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 41.3±2.9 ug/mL chlorophyll (at 105 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) --- 5.01 mg/g astaxanthin content ⁸⁴	C16:0 22.4% ³⁸ C16:1 0.6% C16:2 2.1% C16:3 3.1% C16:4 5.8% C18:0 0.9% C18:1 19.5% C18:2 28.7% C18:3 12.6% other 4.3%

8.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *H. pluvialis* AC136, 143, 587, 588
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *H. pluvialis* BEA 1360B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:

 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:

 - *Chlorella*, ***Haematococcus***, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education
Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ⁵⁰, ***Haematococcus pluvialis*** ⁵⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.] ⁵⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ⁷⁷

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigelowiella natans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium baillyanum* ⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina* ^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁶²,

*Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [Microalgae group at Centro de Investigaciones Científicas Avanzadas \(CICA\), University of A Coruña](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, genomics, monitoring. Research outputs involving microalgae at University of A Coruña include (but are not limited to):

- *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*²¹, *Dunaliella salina*²², ***Haematococcus pluvialis***²³

Location: A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture⁷². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from⁷³:

- *Dunaliella salina*, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*⁷³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: SME

Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:

- *Spirulina*, ***Haematococcus pluvialis***, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Tetraselmis suecica*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.

Location: Worcester, United Kingdom

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9. *Scenedesmus obliquus*

A freshwater green unicellular microalga belonging to the class Chlorophyceae. Its cells can be grouped to form colonies and they are non-motile. It is one of the most widely used lipid-producing microalgae ⁸⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
FACHB 416, SJTU-3

9.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ⁸⁸ <i>from laboratory of live food culture, Institute of Tropical Aquaculture, University Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia.</i>	System: 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks in outdoor natural conditions Medium: BBM Temperature: 17-34°C Light: nd Environmental light/dark cycle	nd	nd	1.50 x 10 ⁷ (cell/mL)
nd ⁸⁸ <i>from laboratory of live food culture, Institute of Tropical Aquaculture, University Malaysia Terengganu, Malaysia.</i>	System: 1 L Erlenmeyer flasks, laboratory control conditions Medium: BBM Temperature: 25°C Light: 2000 μmol/m ² /s, Continuous light	nd	nd	2.80 x 10 ⁷ (cell/mL)
FACHB 416 ⁸⁹	System: 250 mL conical flasks. Medium: BG-11 medium + 0, 25, 50, 100, 200, 500 mg/L linear alkylbenzene sulfonate (LAS) Temperature: 25°C Light: 50 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	1.60 x 10 ⁷ (cell/mL) (at LAS concentrations <100 mg/L)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

9.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
<i>Outdoor natural conditions</i> ⁸⁸ 30.7±0.01% protein ~20±0.0% lipid ~20±0.0% carbohydrates			
<i>Control conditions</i> ⁸⁸ 37.7±0.02% protein ~37±0.0% lipid 38.2±0.02% carbohydrates ---	nd	nd	C15:0 3.3% ⁸⁹ C16:0 22.6% C18:0 1.8% C18:1 8.6% C18:2 3.5% C18:3 47.7% C20:5 10.4% C22:0 2.1%
--- 26.9 ± 3.8% protein ⁹⁰ 12.7 ± 1.3% lipid 11.9 ± 1.1% carbohydrate ---			
25 mg/L LAS treatment ⁸⁹ 24.0% lipid			

9.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Scenedesmus* sp. BEA 0146/1, 0146/2, 0579B, 0380, 0146B, 0580B, 0381, 0838B, 0333, 0562, 0334, 0354, 0565
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology.
 Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):
 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*⁹¹, *Arthrospira maxima*⁹², *Nannochloropsis* spp.⁹³, *Micractinum inermum*¹⁴, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{42,43}, *Nosctoc* sp., *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.**Location:** Swansea, UK

- Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ⁹⁴:

 - *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France
- Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Botryococcus braunii* ⁹⁵, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁹⁶, [*Chlorella vulgaris, Chlorella kessleri, Chlorella sorokiniana, Scenedesmus obliquus*] ⁹⁷

Location: Cádiz, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigeloviella natans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum* ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like* ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarachnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium baillyanum* ⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina* ^{62,65}, *Dunaliella sp.* ⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁶², *Nitzschia sp.* ⁶², *Odontella aurita* ⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum (Porphyridium cruentum)* ^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁶², *Rhodomonas salina* ^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁶², ***Scenedesmus obliquus*** ⁶², *Skeletonema grethae* ⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁷¹, *Euglena proxima* ⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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- Name:** [uFraction8](#)

Business/organisation type: start-up, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: technology, harvesting. The start-up company is developing technologies suitable for biomass filtration, separation, and de-watering. The start-up has tested their innovative solution with *Scenedesmus*, although their innovative solution can be used for a wide range of microorganisms.

Locations: Falkirk, Scotland

- Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.

Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Nannochloropsis, Dunaliella, Nostoc, Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

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10. *Scenedesmus quadricauda*

A freshwater green unicellular microalga belonging to the class Chlorophyceae. It can grow in wide range of industrial waste waters with reasonably good adaptation ability⁹⁸ and it is considered a versatile biofuel feedstock⁹⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
ABU12

10.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
ABU12 ¹⁰⁰	System: 200 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: BBM Temperature: 23±2°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	~0.75
nd ⁹⁸	System: 7 L tank. Medium: Wastewater (from Shek Wu Hui Sewage Treatment Works) Temperature: 28°C Light: 7000 lux, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	0.995 (acclimated culture) 0.940 (non-acclimated culture)
nd ¹⁰¹ from reservoirs in the region of Fez (northern Morocco)	System: Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: synthetic medium Temperature: 20-25°C Light: 300 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	nd	~0.99	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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10.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
<p><i>Acclimated culture</i>⁹⁸ ~20.0% lipid</p> <p><i>Non-acclimated cultures</i> ~18.0% lipid</p> <p>---</p> <p>4.38 – 9.55% protein¹⁰¹ 6.91 – 10.60% lipid 3.67 – 24.76% carbohydrates</p>	nd	<p><i>Acclimated culture</i>⁹⁸ ~5.5mg/L chlorophyll-a</p> <p><i>Non-acclimated culture</i> ~5.3mg/L chlorophyll-a</p>	<p><i>Acclimated culture</i>⁹⁸ C14:0 0.7% C16:0 50.4% C16:1 1.6% C18:0 3.1% C18:1n9 3.0% C18:2n6 24.3% C18:3n3 14.6% C18:3n6 2.3%</p> <p><i>Non-acclimated culture</i> C14:0 0.9% C16:0 55.6% C16:1 2.4% C18:0 1.5% C18:1n9 3.3% C18:2n6 19.9% C18:3n3 14.4% C18:3n6 2.1%</p>

10.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *S. quadricauda* CCAP 276/16, 276/21
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Scenedesmus* sp. BEA 0146/1, 0146/2, 0579B, 0380, 0146B, 0580B, 0381, 0838B, 0333, 0562, 0334, 0354, 0565
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae⁹⁴:
 - *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*
Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.
Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - Spirulina, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena***Location:** Almería, Spain

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11. *Selenastrum capricornutum*

A unicellular freshwater green microalga belonging to the class of Chlorophyceae. It presents fast growth and a moderate sensitivity to toxic compounds. *S. capricornutum* has been described as a new promising microalga for biodiesel production due to its fatty acid composition¹⁰².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 1648.

11.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ^u <i>from the laboratory of the Regional Environmental Protection Agency, Perugia Italy (ARPA)</i>	System: 12 L cylindrical photobioreactor Medium: four nutrient solutions and deionized water Temperature: 22 ± 1°C Light: 140 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	2.4
UTEX 1648 ¹⁰³	System: 75 L, 40 cm high plastic round containers Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 23-40°C Light: nd	nd	37.6 g/m ² /d	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

11.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
17.5% lipids ¹⁰² --- 32.3-38.4% protein ¹⁰³ 11.8 ± 34.6% lipid 33-49.8% carbohydrate	nd	nd	C14:0 0.17% ¹⁰² C16:0 19.57% C16:1 0.32% C18:0 1.26% C18:1 54.82% C18:2 4.30% C18:3 6.10% C20:1 0.55% C20:3 1.19%

11.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *S. capricornutum* CCAP 278/5
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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Class: Trebouxiophyceae

12. *Auxenochlorella protothecoides*

Formerly known as *Chlorella protothecoides* (Krüger)³³. A eukaryotic green microalga belonging to Trebouxiophyceae class. It can grow either photoautotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically¹⁰⁴. *C. protothecoides* shows a high industrial potential for producing lipids and fatty acids at high yield¹⁰⁵.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 249, SAG 211-7b

12.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
UTEX 249 ¹⁰⁴	System: 250 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: BBM Carbon source: glucose, glycerol, or acetate Light: 16h L: 8h D (autotrophic and mixotrophic) and 24h D (heterotrophic)	nd	1.59±0.50 (on glucose/acetate; 80:20)	4.76±1.50 (on glucose/acetate; 80:20)
nd ¹⁰⁵	System: 2.8 L glass flasks (PYREX) Medium: Modified BBM Temperature: 28°C Carbon source: CO ₂ , and glucose Light: 60 μmol m ⁻² s ⁻¹ L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	9.54 ± 0.72 (mixotrophic cultures) 10.32 ± 0.83 (heterotrophic cultures)
nd ¹⁰⁶ obtained from Culture Collection of Alga at the University of Texas	System: Shaking flasks / 5 L bioreactor Medium: BBM Temperature: 28°C Carbon source: glucose Light: 5 μmol/m ² /s L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	51.2 (in improve fed-batch culture)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

12.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
52% lipids ¹⁰⁴	nd	nd	nd

12.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. protothecoides* CCAP 211/11I, 211/13, 211/17, 211/54, 211/7A, 2117C, 211/7D, 211/8D
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

13. *Botryococcus braunii*

A eukaryotic planktonic Trebouxiophyceae strain, naturally found in freshwater and brackish ponds, that is typically a very slow growing microalga due to the high production of triterpene hydrocarbon oils with applications for various classes of biofuel (petroleum, kerosene, diesel) production by hydrocracking. There are a wide variety of *Botryococcus* strains (races) with very diverse oil productivities¹⁰⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCAP 807/2, SAG 30.81, CCALA 777, CCALA 778, CCALA 835, UTEX Bb 572, AC755, AC759, AC760, AC761, AC765¹⁰⁸

13.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 807/2 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: 3N-BBM Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.027	0.098	1.94
AC755 ¹⁰⁸	System: Bubble column PBR (0.4 L) Medium: Chu 13 medium Temperature: 23°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 18h L: 6h D	nd	0.06	~1.75
AC759			0.09	~2.75
AC761			0.15	~3.6
CCALA 777			0.08	~2.2
CCALA 778			0.12	~3.6
CCAP 807/2			0.14	~4.6

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

13.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
40% protein ³⁸ 33% lipid 6% carbohydrate	nd	6% α-carotene ¹⁰⁹ 6% β-carotene 22% lutein	C16:0 29.5% ³⁸ C16:1 3.3% C18:0 1.0% C18:1 44.9% C18:2 21.1% other 0.3%

13.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *B. braunii* AC754, AC755 to AC761, AC763, AC767, AC768
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *B. braunii* 807/1, 807/2
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Botryococcus* sp. A12.415 (not-distributed), A13-394 (not-distributed), CCMP2742
Location: Roscoff, France
- **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *B. braunii* BEA 0649B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Botryococcus braunii*⁹⁵, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁹⁶, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]⁹⁷**Location:** Cádiz, Spain

14. *Chlorella sorokiniana*

A eukaryotic freshwater Trebouxiophyceae strain with fast growth rate with applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically ^{110,111}. Some *C. sorokiniana* show a broad temperature range and thermotolerance up to 45°C ¹¹².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 1230, UTEX 1602, UTEX 3016, UTEX 2805, IBVF 211-32

14.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
UTEX 1230 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: 3N-BBM Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.115	0.185	3.7
IBVF 211-32 ¹¹³	System: 2 L stirred tank reactor (STR) Medium: Sueoka medium Carbon source: CO ₂ , and acetate Temperature: 25°C Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous light	nd	1.16	1.18 (on CO ₂) ~3.1 (on acetate)
UTEX 1602 ¹¹⁴	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: Kuhl medium Carbon source: 1 % CO ₂ , glucose Temperature: 25°C Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous light	nd	nd	0.68 (on CO ₂) 5.08 (on glucose)
UTEX 2805 ¹¹⁵	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: synthetic medium Temperature: 27°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	2.11±0.26 x 10 ⁶ (cell/mL)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

14.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
56% protein ³⁸ 22% lipid 17% carbohydrate --- 6.65% lipids (on CO ₂) ¹¹⁴ 31.58% lipids (on glucose) --- 40% lipids ¹¹³	46% C ³⁸ 2% N C/N ratio 21	32.4 mg/g total chlorophyll ³⁸ 1.2 mg/g beta-carotene 7.1 mg/g lutein	C16:0 22.0% ³⁸ C16:1 4.3% C16:2 11.5% C16:3 5.1% C18:0 3.5% C18:1 11.3% C18:2 31.1% C18:3 9.1% other 2.1% --- C16:0 20.99% ¹¹⁴ C16:1 5.56% C16:2 4.82% C18:0 0.33% C18:1 2.95% C18:2 13.79% C18:3 33.31%

Additional biomass considerations:

Supplementation of glucose as a carbon source can increase cell density, biomass production and total lipid yield but decreases protein abundance and chlorophyll biosynthesis ²⁹.

14.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. sorokiniana* 211/8K
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. sorokiniana* BEA 0002 to 0004, BEA 0022, BEA 0302, BEA 0665B, BEA 0061, BEA 0665B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain
Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii*⁹⁵, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁹⁶, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]⁹⁷

Location: Cádiz, Spain

- **Name:** [Laboratoire GEnie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, higher education
Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Chlorella vulgaris*¹¹⁶, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***¹¹⁷, *Parachlorella kessleri*¹¹⁸, *Nannochloropsis oculata*¹¹⁶

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.
Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - Spirulina, ***Chlorella***, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: SME
Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:
 - Spirulina, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Tetraselmis suecica*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.

Location: Worcester, United Kingdom

- **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on¹¹⁹:
 - *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, ***Chlorella sorokiniana***, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyl, Scotland

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15. *Chlorella vulgaris*

A eukaryotic marine Trebouxiophyceae strain that has large-scale commercial cultivation in Asia as a high protein-rich food and feed source, a nutritional supplement, and biofuel source. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically^{120–122}. It has quite robust growth for cultivation in open ponds as well as photobioreactors¹²³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCAP 211/8K, CCAP 211/11B, CCAP 211/21A, CCAP 211/21B, CCAP 211/79, UTEX 2805, UTEX 2714

15.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 211/79 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.18	0.428	3.0
UTEX 2805 ¹¹⁵	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: synthetic medium Temperature: 27°C Light: 60 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	3.2±0.5 x 10 ⁶ cell/mL
UTEX 2714 ¹²⁴	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: modified/optimised synthetic medium Carbon source: glucose/glycerol Temperature: 26°C Light: 60 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	1.87	5.62
nd ¹²⁵ <i>purchased from Connecticut Valley Biological Supply Co. Inc</i>	System: PBR (3.8 gallon, 6 L working volume) Medium: BBM Temperature: 25°C Light: 276 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	0.35	~1.6

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

15.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
58% protein ³⁸ 12% lipid 17% carbohydrate ---	52% C ³⁸ 3% N C/N ratio 19	22.6 mg/g total chlorophyll ³⁸ 2.7 mg/g total carotenoid	C14:0 3.1% ³⁸ C16:0 25.1% C16:1 5.3% C16:3 1.3% C18:0 0.6% C18:1 12.6% C18:2 7.2% C18:3 19.1% C20:3 0.8% other 24% ---
51-58% protein ⁵³ 14-22% lipid 12-17% carbohydrate ---			C14:0 3.01% ¹²⁶ C16:0 16.99% C16:1 13.61% C16:2 5.47% C16:3 7.93% C18:0 1.51% C18:1 8.55% C18:2 14.44% C18:3 16.63% C20:4 1.24% C20:5 10.17%
40.10% lipid ¹²⁴			

15.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. vulgaris* AC149, AC150, AC873
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: multiple, including *C. vulgaris* 211/21A, 211/21B, 211/109 to 211/114, 211/79 to 211/82
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. vulgaris* BEA 0753B, BEA 0755B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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MICROALGAE

Interreg
Atlantic Area
European Regional Development Fund

EUROPEAN UNION

- **Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology.

Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus obliquus* and ***Chlorella vulgaris*** ⁹¹, *Arthrospira maxima* ⁹², *Nannochloropsis* spp. ⁹³, *Micractinium inermum* ¹⁴, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{42,43}, *Nosctoc* sp., *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

- **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., ***Chlorella vulgaris***, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissfloi*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ⁹⁴:

- *Spirulina*, ***Chlorella***, *Scenedesmus*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

- **Name:** [Alver World SA](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: Producer, limited company

Expertise: Food technology company that is specialised in development of *Chlorella* strains and contribution into various food products. Their patented ***Chlorella vulgaris*** strains include:

- CCAP 211/137 (White *Chlorella* E14b1), CCAP 211/138 (Yellow *Chlorella* E1b0), CCAP 211/139 (Yellow *Chlorella* E2b0)

Location: Saint-Aubin, Switzerland

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- Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Botryococcus braunii*⁹⁵, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁹⁶, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]⁹⁷

Location: Cádiz, Spain
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of⁸⁶:

 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [Biorea](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: Aquaculture; Cosmetics; Feed; Food; Nutraceuticals; Biotechnology. They specialise in *Chlorella* production, but support customers with R&D and production of tailor-made biomass in their patented airlift bioreactors. See their market offer in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Locations: Lamballe, France
- Name:** [Buggypower](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organization type: producer, research & development, downstream processing

Expertise: feed, food, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company specialises in¹²⁷:

 - *Chlorella*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Rhodomonas*

Location: Lisbon, Portugal (shared services centre & Alguimya store); Funchal, Portugal (Financial office); Porto Santo, Portugal (Buggypower production unit in partnership with Electricity Company of Madeira); San Pedro del Pinatar, Spain (Financial office); Lorqui, Spain (Research and development pilot plant)
- Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Scenedesmus subspicatus*¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{13,14}, *Dunaliella salina*^{13,15,16}, *Micractinum inermum*¹³, ***Chlorella vulgaris***^{17,18}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*^{19,20}, *Nannochloropsis salina*¹⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*²⁰

Location: Sheffield, UK

- **Name:** [Laboratoire GENie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development, higher education

Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- ***Chlorella vulgaris***¹¹⁶, *Chlorella sorokiniana*¹¹⁷, *Parachlorella kessleri*¹¹⁸, *Nannochloropsis oculata*¹¹⁶

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like*⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², ***Chlorella vulgaris***⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella sp.*⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia sp.*⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum (Porphyridium cruentum)*^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture⁷². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from⁷³:

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- *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, ***Chlorella vulgaris***, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*⁷³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

- **Name:** [Research and training centre of LLDC Algae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: large-scale development. Their range of products include *Chlorella*-based animal feed (Greenfeed¹²⁸) and vitamin B12 for human use (Greenbloom¹²⁹).

Locations: Bréhan, France

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.

Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- Spirulina, ***Chlorella***, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: SME

Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:

- Spirulina, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Nannochloropsis sp.*, *Tetraselmis suecica*, ***Chlorella vulgaris***, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.

Location: Worcester, United Kingdom

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Atlantic Area
European Regional Development Fund

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16. Jaagichlorella luteoviridis

Formerly known as *Chlorella luteoviridis* (Chodat) ¹³⁰. A eukaryotic freshwater Trebouxiophyceae strain (also known as *Heterochlorella luteoviridis* or *Jaagichlorella luteoviridis*) with fast growth rate and along with other *Chlorella* sp. has applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically ¹³¹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 211/3, CCAP 211/4, CCAP 211/5B

16.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 211/3 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: Jaworski's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.29	0.36	2.52
Indigenous wastewater <i>C. luteoviridis</i> strain ¹³²	System: 250 mL conical flasks (batch; semi-continuous) Medium: Raw municipal wastewater secondary treated effluent (RMWSE) + 25 % v/v sludge liquor Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	nd	~0.8 <i>(batch)</i> 1.78 <i>(semi-continuous)</i>	0.84 <i>(batch)</i> 6.01-7.99 <i>(semi-continuous)</i>
Indigenous wastewater <i>C. luteoviridis</i> strain ¹³²	System: Open pond (150 L, 10 cm depth) Medium: RMWSE + 25 % v/v/ sludge liquor Temperature: outdoors Light: outdoors	nd	~0.31 <i>(in summer)</i> ~0.25 <i>(in spring)</i>	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

16.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
47% protein ³⁸ 22% lipid 12% carbohydrate	nd	29.8 mg/g total chlorophyll ³⁸ 3.4 mg/g total carotenoid	C14:0 2.4% ³⁸ C16:0 25.0% C16:1 9.3% C18:0 7.2% C18:1 21.3% C18:2 9.7% C18:3 24.9% other 0.2%

16.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *J. luteoviridis* CCAP 211/10A, 211/10C, 211/10E, 211/3, 211/4, 211/5B
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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Interreg
Atlantic Area
European Regional Development Fund

EUROPEAN UNION

17. *Parachlorella kessleri*

A eukaryotic freshwater Trebouxiophyceae strain with potential applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel. It can be cultivated autotrophically, mixotrophically or heterotrophically¹³³. *Chlorella kessleri* (Fott & Nováková) is considered to be a synonym of *Parachlorella kessleri*³³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 211/11G, QWY28, GB1

17.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 211/11G ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: Jaworki's medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.36	0.413	2.74
QWY28 ¹³⁴ collected from rivers in the district of Harbin city, China	System: Conical flasks Medium: Artificial seawater Temperature: 30°C Light: 200 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	0.633±0.027	3.8
QWY28 ¹³⁴ collected from rivers in the district of Harbin city, China	System: 500 mL glass vessels, 2.5 % CO ₂ Medium: Raw swine wastewater Temperature: 27-30°C Light: 200 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	0.775±0.026	6.2
QWY28 ¹³⁴ collected from rivers in the district of Harbin city, China	System: 500 mL glass vessels, 2.5 % CO ₂ Medium: Raw swine wastewater Temperature: 27-30°C Light: 600 μmol/m ² /s, L:D cycle nd	nd	1.150±0.056	9.2

GB1 ¹³⁵ GenBank KX151669.1	System: 500 mL flasks (200 mL working volume)	nd	0.176±0.00 (<i>phototrophic</i>)	1.043±0.02 (<i>phototrophic</i>)
	Medium: BG11		1.362±0.01 (<i>mixotrophic</i>)	8.176±0.06 (<i>mixotrophic</i>)
	Carbon source: glucose Temperature: 25±2°C Light: 28 µmol/m ² /s, Continuous		1.311±0.01 (<i>heterotrophic</i>)	7.871±0.09 (<i>heterotrophic</i>)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

17.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
51% protein ³⁸ 25% lipid 16% carbohydrate ---	nd	23.6 mg/g total chlorophyll ³⁸ 4.1 mg/g total carotenoid ---	C14:0 1.1% ³⁸ C16:0 12.1% C16:1 7.2% C18:0 4.2%
54% carbohydrate ¹³⁴ (of which ~35% is glucose) ---		9.17±0.11 mg/g Chlorophyll a ¹³⁵ 3.98±0.02 mg/g Chlorophyll b 2.60±0.02 mg/g carotenoids	C18:1 24.2% C18:2 23.5% C18:3 26.8% C20:0 0.5% other 2.1%
41.29±0.90% protein ¹³⁵ 20.14±0.58% lipid 34.15±0.42% carbohydrate			

17.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Parachlorella* sp. BEA 0045, 0046, 0047B, 0060,
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain
Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Botryococcus braunii*⁹⁵, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁹⁶, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*]⁹⁷**Location:** Cádiz, Spain

- **Name:** [Laboratoire GEnie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, higher education
Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Chlorella vulgaris*¹¹⁶, *Chlorella sorokiniana*¹¹⁷, *Parachlorella kessleri*¹¹⁸,
*Nannochloropsis oculata*¹¹⁶
- Location:** Saint-Nazaire, France

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Atlantic Area
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18. *Picochlorum* sp.

Green microalgae which is able to cope with environmental perturbations, thriving in freshwater as well as in 3-fold the salinity of seawater, and in a wide range of light intensities (80-2000 $\mu\text{E}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$), and temperatures (16-33°C). *Picochlorum* species present huge biotechnological interest since they are characterised by high biomass production, high protein and carotenoid content, and lipid accumulation ¹³⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include: SENEW3, QUCCCM 127.

18.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹³⁷	System: 400 mL square Pyrex bottles Medium: filter sterilized seawater, enriched with trace nutrients Carbon source: 0.75–1% CO ₂ Temperature: 29–33 °C Light: 900-2000 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, L: D cycle nd	nd	~100 g/m ² /d	nd
QUCCCM 127 ¹³⁸	System: DASGIP parallel bioreactor system Medium: supplemented sea water Temperature: 30-45°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D cycle	nd	98.3 (35 °C) 250 (20% CO ₂)	nd

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

ENHANCE
MICROALGAE

Interreg
Atlantic Area
European Regional Development Fund

EUROPEAN UNION

18.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
55-58% protein ¹³⁸ 24-28% lipid 9-14% carbohydrate	51% C ^t 12% N	~9% total chlorophyll ¹³⁷ content	C14:0 0.40-0.59% ¹³⁸ C16:0 17.6-22% C16:1 0.19-0.26% C18:0 1.39-1.68% C18:1 1-2.22% C18:2 17.45-24% C20:1 48.55-59.94% C20:5 0.58-1.14% C22:1 0.86-1.11%

18.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. oculatum* AC142, *P. maculatum* AC627
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Picochlorum* sp. CCAP 6079/1
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. atomus* CCMP508, *P. costavermella* BCC143000, *Picochlorum* sp. (various)
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. eukaryotum* BEA 0756B, *P. maculatum* BEA 0741B, *P. oklahemense* BEA BEA 0398, 0399, 0400, 0401, 0402, 0421, 0422, 0654B, 0153B, 0154B, 0155B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

Class: Chlorodendrophyceae

19. *Tetraselmis subcordiformis*

A marine unicellular green microalga with a cell size of 10–20 μm that is a widely used feed in aquaculture for its high nutrient levels. It has been proven to accumulate starch autotrophically or mixotrophically ^{139,140}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
FACHB-1751

19.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
FACHB-1751 ¹⁴¹	System: 600 mL glass air bubble column PBR (500 mL working volume) Medium: ASW (<i>P</i> deprivation and <i>P</i> repletion) Temperature: 25°C Light: 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light	nd	0.68±0.13 (<i>P</i> -deprivation recultivated in <i>P</i> -replete medium)	5.3±0.4 (<i>P</i> -deprivation recultivated in <i>P</i> -replete medium)
nd ¹⁴² from the Culture Collection of Microalgae at Shanghai Ocean University in China	System: 60 L PBR Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 15, 20, 25, 30 °C Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light	nd	nd	~0.10 d ⁻¹ (at 20°C)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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Interreg
Atlantic Area
European Regional Development Fund

EUROPEAN UNION

19.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
46.9±1.9% starch ¹⁴¹ <i>(P-deprivation recultivated in P-replete medium)</i> --- 22.25% lipid ¹⁴² <i>(at 20°C)</i> --- 18.0 ± 0.3% protein ⁹⁰ 10.7 ± 0.8% lipid 47.4 ± 1.4% carbohydrate	nd	nd	C16:0 14.93–18.49% ¹⁴² C16:3n3 6.77–12.30% C18:3n3 15.99–23.65% C20:0 9.04– 10.09%

19.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. AC255, AC260, AC264, AC802
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. subcordiformis* CCAP 161/1A, 161/1B, 161/3
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. (various)
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. BEA 0647B, 0076B, 0648B, 0098/1, 1321B, 0098/2, 1323B, 0098B, 0754B, 0758B, 0646B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:

 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., **Tetraselmis** sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal
- Name:** [Algalimento](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of ⁵⁵:

 - **Tetraselmis** sp., *Spirulina canariensis*, *Dunaliella salina*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal
- Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ⁹⁴:

 - *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, **Tetraselmis**, *Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:

 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, **Tetraselmis**, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education

Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ⁵⁰, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁵⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis sp.*] ⁵⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ⁷⁷

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁴³:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

- **Name:** [Sparos](#)

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, ecophysiology, genomics. Research outputs associated to the company include (but are not limited to):

- *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ¹⁴⁴, *Tetraselmis sp.* ¹⁴⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ¹⁴⁶

Location: Olhão, Portugal

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20. *Tetraselmis suecica*

A marine unicellular green microalga. It is a motile chlorophyte that can be used as a feedstock in aquaculture due to its high lipid content. *T. suecica* can be also used to treat wastewater¹⁴⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CS187

20.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CS187 ¹⁴⁷	System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: seawater and anaerobically-digested piggery effluent (ADPE) Temperature: 25 ± 1°C Light: 175 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D cycle	nd	59.8 mg/L/d	nd
nd ¹⁴⁸ from NLP Corp. (Busan, Korea)	System: 20-L circular cylindrical tank Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20 ± 1°C Light: 36.3, 60.5, 84.7, 108.9, 133.1 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	0.89 (at 108.9 µmol/m ² /s) 1.1 (at 18.5 mg/L Nitrogen)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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20.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
~30mg/L/d lipid ¹⁴⁷ ~7mg/L/d carbohydrate --- 17.28% protein ¹⁴⁸	nd	1.5% chlorophyll ¹⁴⁷ content	C16:0 ~55.0% ¹⁴⁸ C18:0 ~1.0% C18:1 ~20.0% C18:2(6) ~2.0% C18:3 ~0.8%

20.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. suecica* AC254, *Tetraselmis* sp. AC255, AC260, AC264, AC802
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. suecica* CCAP 66/22A, 66/22B, 66/22C, 66/22D, 66/38, 66/4
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. suecica* TS-Droze, *Tetraselmis* sp. (various)
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Tetraselmis* sp. BEA 0647B, 0076B, 0648B, 0098/1, 1321B, 0098/2, 1323B, 0098B, 0754B, 0758B, 0646B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Algalimento](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of ⁵⁵:
 - *Tetraselmis* sp., *Spirulina canariensis*, *Dunaliella salina***Locations:** Lisbon, Portugal

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- **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ⁹⁴:
 - *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

- **Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education
Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - [*Dunaliella salina, Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ⁵⁰, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁵⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica, Tetraselmis* sp.] ⁵⁷ *Rhodomonas lens* ⁷⁷

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigeloviella natans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium baillyanum* ⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina* ^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi* ⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁶², *Nitzschia* sp. ⁶², *Odontella aurita* ⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁶², *Rhodomonas salina* ^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁶², *Skeletonema grethae* ⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁷¹, *Euglena proxima* ⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

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Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁴³:

- *Nannochloropsis*, ***Tetraselmis***, *Isochrysis*, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: SME

Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:

- *Spirulina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Nannochloropsis sp.*, ***Tetraselmis suecica***, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.

Location: Worcester, United Kingdom

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Bacillariophyta (Diatoms)

Diatoms are the most species-rich group of eukaryotic algae, representing approximately 40% of global marine biomass production and 25% of terrestrial primary production¹⁴⁹. The phylum is divided into three classes, with Mediophyceae and Coscinodiscophyceae comprising the centric diatoms and Bacillariophyceae the pennate diatoms. While centric diatoms are mainly present in marine habitats, pennate forms are distributed relatively evenly in freshwater and marine environments. Diatoms contain unique cell walls composed of silica and known as frustules, often requiring the addition of silica to the growth medium¹⁴⁹.

Major classes

No. of species in Algaebase

Mediophyceae

1872

Bacillariophyceae

14448

Coscinodiscophyceae

157

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above

Class: Mediophyceae (pennate diatoms)

21. *Chaetoceros calcitrans*

A marine planktonic diatom. It is a roughly cylindrical alga, elliptical in valve view and rectangular in girdle view. The cells bear long cell wall prolongations (seta) at their poles which join cells together to form chains.

C. calcitrans (Paulsen) Takano is known as a potential species for producing biodiesel¹⁵⁰, with high growth rates even at low light intensities¹⁵¹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCMP 60/00/00 1315, CCAP 1010/11, CCMP1315; NEPCC 590; PLY537, UPMAAHU10.

21.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP 60/00/00 1315 ¹⁵¹	System: 16-29 L bags Medium: Conway Carbon source: 0.2% CO ₂ Temperature: 20-23°C Light: 750–1000 lx, continuous light	nd	nd	7-13x10 ⁶ cells/mL
UPMAAHU10 152	System: 1 L flasks (outdoors and lab) Medium: Conway Temperature: 24-36°C (outdoors); 23°C (lab) Light: 140 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D (outdoors); 150 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D (lab).	nd	nd	2.50±0.20 (outdoors) 2.20±0.10 (lab)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

21.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Protein: ¹⁵² - 41.60% (outdoors); - 43.10% (lab) Lipid: - 26.80% (outdoors); - 11.71% (lab) Carbohydrate: - 8.70% (outdoors); - 6.62% (lab)	nd	nd	C14:0 18.0% ¹⁵¹ C16:0 13.6% ΣSFA 34.4% C16:1(n-7) 27.6% C18:1 (n-9) 0.7% ΣMUFA 30.0% C18:3 (n-3) 0.1% C18:4 (n-3) 2.1% EPA 16.3% DHA 0.4% Σ(n-3) 19.1% 16:3 (n-4) 14.6% 18:2 (n-6) 0.4% ΣPUFA 35.6%

21.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. calcitrans* AC165
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. calcitrans* Arg 11, Arg 13, *Chaetoceros* sp.
Location: Roscoff, France
- **Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. calcitrans* 1085/3
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- **Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPESCA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator

Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to) ^{153,154}:

- ***Chaetoceros calcitrans***, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrams*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Location: Vigo, Spain

- **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:

- *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, ***Chaetoceros***, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigelowiella natans* ⁶², ***Chaetoceros calcitrans*** ⁶², ***Chaetoceros calcitrans f. pumillum*** ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros sp. Tenuissimus like* ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium baillyanum* ⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina* ^{62,65}, *Dunaliella sp.* ⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi* ⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁶², *Nitzschia sp.* ⁶², *Odontella aurita* ⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum (Porphyridium cruentum)* ^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁶², *Rhodomonas salina* ^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁶², *Skeletonema grethae* ⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁷¹, *Euglena proxima* ⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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- **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on ¹¹⁹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnoraphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

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22. *Cyclotella* sp.

A genus of freshwater diatoms with a high biomass lipid content, along with reasonably high biomass productivities under outdoor conditions¹⁵⁵. They can grow phototrophically, heterotrophically or mixotrophically.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCMP 331, CCMP 332, UTEX 1269

22.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
<i>C. cryptica</i> CCMP 331 ¹⁵⁶	System: 2L polycarbonate carboy Medium: F/2 medium Carbon source: air or 1g/L glucose Temperature: 20°C Light: 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 14:10h L:D or no light	nd	nd	0.58
CYCLOJ ¹⁵⁷	System: 1L Roux bottles Medium: enriched seawater Carbon source: CO ₂ 0.5% Temperature: 28°C Light: 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous	nd	nd	0.239 (<i>exponential</i>) 0.922 (<i>stationary</i>)
UTEX 1269 ¹⁵⁵	System: 4.5L bubble column PBR (10.4 cm diameter, 69 cm height) Medium: Harrison's ASM Carbon source: CO ₂ 200 to 3000 ppm Temperature: 22°C Light: 46-127 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ continuous illumination	nd	0.195	1.025

<i>C. cryptica</i> CCMP 332 ¹⁵⁸	System: 50 mL culture flasks	nd	nd	0.23 (phototrophic)
	Medium: f/2 medium			0.32 (heterotrophic)
	Carbon source: none or 2 g/L glucose Temperature: 20°C Light: 40 μmol/m ² /s, 12:12h L:D or none			2.02 (mixotrophic)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

22.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile	
23% lipid 8.5% chitin ¹⁵⁵	nd	chlorophyll α: 3.6 mg/L (exponential phase)	C14:0 5.5% C16:0 11.4% C16:3(n-4) 21.0% C16:2(n-4) 6.4% C16:1(n-7) 28.6% C20:5(n-3) 19.4% C22:6(n-3) 4.8% (autotrophic)	
2% protein 0.2% carbohydrate 2% lipid (phototrophic)			27 mg/L (stationary phase) ¹⁵⁷	C14:0 2.5% C16:0 16.6% C16:3(n-4) 1.1% C16:2(n-4) 0% C16:1(n-7) 60.7% C20:5(n-3) 15.1% C22:6(n-3) 1.6% (heterotrophic) ¹⁵⁶
7% protein 3% carbohydrate 0.3% lipid (heterotrophic)				
6% protein 1% carbohydrate 3% lipid (mixotrophic) ¹⁵⁸				

22.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Cyclotella* sp. CCAP 1070/4, *C. cryptica* CCAP 1070/2
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Cyclotella* sp. RCC1715, 1865, 4502, 4824
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Cyclotella* sp. BEA 0730B, *C. aff. meduanae* BEA 0731B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

23. *Odontella aurita*

A marine diatom with interest as a nutritional supplement, and pharmaceutical applications due to its fatty acid characteristics, in particular the accumulation of polyunsaturated fatty acids ¹⁵⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1054/1, SCCAP K 1251

23.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1054/1 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: f/2 + Si medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.001	0.011	0.2
SCCAP K1251 ¹⁶⁰	System: PBR (1.2 L working volume) Medium: Modified L1 medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s for 1 st two days, then 300 µmol/m ² /s continuous	nd	nd	3.95 <i>(low nitrogen)</i> 5.84 <i>(high nitrogen)</i>
SCCAP K1251 ¹⁶¹	System: Glass column (300 mL working volume) Medium: Artificial seawater enriched with L1 medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 150 µmol/m ² /s Continuous	nd	nd	6.34 <i>(high nitrogen)</i> 6.58 <i>(high phosphorous)</i>

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

23.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
48% protein ³⁸ 5% lipid 20% carbohydrate ---			C14:0 27.2% ³⁸ C16:0 7.7% C16:1 18.7% C16:2 3.1% C16:3 5.7% C16:4 3.1% C18:1 1.9% C18:2 1.2% C18:4 0.8% C20:5 22.8% other 7.8%
~25% protein ¹⁶⁰ ~10% lipids 60.33% Chrysolaminarin (carbohydrate) ---	30% C ³⁸ 5% N C/N ratio 6.5	2.33% fucoxanthin ¹⁶⁰ (carotenoid) 60.33% Chrysolaminarin	
15.3% protein ¹⁶¹ 15.9% lipid 50.4% carbohydrate 47.2 % β -1,3-glucan			

23.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aurita* AC815, AC816
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aurita* CCAP 1007/3, 1054/1
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aurita* Santec 04, NCC87 D-Od.au. IA1
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Odontella* cf. *aurita* BEA 0932B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², ***Odontella aurita***⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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24. *Skeletonema* sp.

A genus of unicellular marine diatoms that contributes to phytoplankton blooms in marine environments worldwide ¹⁶². The main challenge with cultivation of *Skeletonema* sp. is obtaining a sufficient amount of biomass, since their abundance under laboratory conditions is much lower than in the natural environment ¹⁶³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

GOC27, CIM876, UHO29, CCMP794, CCMP1685, CCMP781, CCAP1077/8, SNZ B202, SNZ B211, SZN B141, 7A3, 14A4 ¹⁶²

24.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁶⁴ <i>Isolated from Vishakhapatnam, India</i>	System: flasks (volume nd) Medium: F/2Si media Carbon source: n.d Temperature: 30°C Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12:12h L:D	nd	nd	0.184
GOC27 ¹⁶⁵ <i>Isolated from the Gulf of Carpenteria, Australia</i>	System: 3L conical flasks Medium: F/2 media Carbon source: nd Temperature: 25°C Light: 80 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$	nd	nd	Growth rate 0.73 h ⁻¹ 15.7 pg/cell
<i>S. grevillei</i> CIM876 ¹⁶³	System: 2L bioreactor Medium: F/2 media Carbon source: air, 1 L/min Temperature: 18°C Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ in 12:12h L:D	nd	nd	0.32
UHO29 ¹⁶⁶	System: 1m ² raceway ponds at 30 cm depth Medium: enriched artificial seawater Carbon source: air Temperature: 26-32°C Light: 60-150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ in 12:12h L:D	nd	0.166	0.52

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

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24.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
53.5% protein 17.1% carbohydrate 27% lipid ¹⁶⁴	nd	1.8 mg/g chlorophyll c 1.2 mg/g carotenoid 0.5 mg/g fucoxanthin ¹⁶⁴	C14:0 7% C16:0 49% C16:1 6.8% C18:0 5.7% C22:6(n-3) 3% ¹⁶⁴
28.1% protein 4% carbohydrate 13.3% lipid ¹⁶⁵			C14:0 16% C16:0 13.7% C16:1(n-7) 22.3% C18:0 2% C20:5(n-3) 12% C22:6(n-3) 1.4% ¹⁶⁵

24.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *S. marioi* AC174
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Skeletonema* sp. CCAP 1077/1B, 1077/1C, *S. grethae* CCAP 1077/3, 1077/4, *S. marinoi* CCAP1077/5, *S. pseudocostatum* CCAP1077/7
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Skeletonema* sp. RCC1866, 1873, 2932, 2940, 4275, 4276, 4492, 4493, 4651, 4652, 4653, 4817, 4819, 4820, 4830, 4832, 4833, 5447, 5502, 5911, 5912, 5913, 7076, 7739, 7740, 7742, *S. costatum* RCC70, 1716, *S. pseudocostatum* RCC7297, 7300, *S. japonicum* RCC74, *S. marinoi* RCC75
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Skeletonema* sp. BEA 0722B, *S. menzelii* BEA 0824B, 0831B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:

 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, ***Skeletonema***, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigeloviella natans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium baillyanum* ⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina* ^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi* ⁶², *Haematococcus pluviialis* ⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁶², *Nitzschia* sp. ⁶², *Odontella aurita* ⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁶², *Rhodomonas salina* ^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁶², ***Skeletonema grethae*** ⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁷¹, *Euglena proxima* ⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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25. *Thalassiosira pseudonana*

A marine diatom strain attractive for its ability to store a significant amount of lipids (up to 45-60% of dry cell weight). It is a model diatom that has been extensively studied to understand fundamental biological processes, as well as for production of valuable natural compounds such as lipids and pigments ¹⁶⁷.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1085/12, CCMP1335, CS-173

25.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CS-173 ¹⁶⁸	System: 2L Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: G ₂ Carbon source: 1% CO ₂ Temperature: 20°C Light: 100 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	13 pg DW/cell (with constant light) 10 pg DW/cell (with 12:12 L:D)
n.d ¹⁶⁹ <i>obtained from M. Hildebrand, SIO</i>	System: Flasks (volume n.d) Medium: Guillard F Carbon source: CO ₂ Temperature: 25°C Light: from 20 to 300 μmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	0.58	2
nd ¹⁷⁰ <i>obtained from the Algae Culture Collection Centre and Laboratory, Universiti Malaysia Pahang</i>	System: 2L Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: F/2 media Carbon source: 1.5% CO ₂ Temperature: 18°C Light: from 40 to 200 μmol/m ² /s blue light, various light periods	nd	nd	1.245 (with 120 μmol/m ² /s blue light)

nd ¹⁶⁴ <i>Isolated from Vishakhapatnam, India</i>	System: Flasks (volume n.d) Medium: F/2Si media Carbon source: n.d Temperature: 30°C Light: 100 µmol/m ² /s, 12:12h L:D	nd	nd	0.166
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

25.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
44% protein 27% carbohydrate 30% lipid ¹⁶⁸	nd	1.18 mg/g fucoxanthin (with 120 µmol/m ² /s blue light and photoperiod of 8:16 L:D) ¹⁷⁰	C20:5(n-3) 24% C22:6(n-3) 5% C14:0 8% C16:0 13% C16:1(n-7) 22% ¹⁶⁸
214.33 mg/g DW protein 181.13 mg/g DW carbohydrate 93.40 mg/g DW lipid ¹⁶⁴	nd	1.45 mg/g fucoxanthin 1.5 mg/g carotenoids 1.95 mg/g chlorophyll ¹⁶⁴	C14:0 8% C14:1 4% C16:0 34% C16:1 19% C17:0 18% C18:0 1.5% C18:1 6% C18:2 1% C18:3 4% C20:1 0.3% C20:4 3% C22:1 0.4% ¹⁷⁰

25.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. pseudonana* CCAP1085/34
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. pseudonana* RCC950
Location: Roscoff, France

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- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus like*⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², ***Thalassiosira pseudonana***⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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Class: Bacillariophyceae (centric diatoms)

26. *Navicula* sp.

A genus of diatoms found in marine and freshwater environments. They can grow heterotrophically, phototrophically or mixotrophically¹⁷¹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCMP 543

26.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
JPCC DA0580 ¹⁷² closest relative <i>N. pelliculosa</i> CCMP 543	System: 500 mL flasks Medium: seawater and f/2 Carbon source: air bubbling Temperature: nd Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous	nd	0.066	0.346
nd ¹⁷³ obtained from the Research Centre for Oceanography, Jakarta	System: 1L air-lift PBR Medium: modified artificial seawater Carbon source: air bubbling Temperature: RT Light: 202 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ in 12:12h L:D	nd	0.153	1.073
nd ¹⁷⁴ obtained from the University of Sonora, Mexico	System: 10L plastic containers Medium: f/2 medium Carbon source: air Temperature: nd Light: 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ continuous light	nd	nd	592 pg/cell (white light) 1607 pg/cell (blue light)

O-48 ¹⁷¹ <i>Isolated from marine water in Japan</i>	System: 300 mL flasks Medium: Guillard F medium Carbon source: 0.04% CO ₂ and 1mM acetic acid Temperature: 20°C Light: 20 μmol/m ² /s continuous light	nd	0.54 mg/L/day	nd
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

26.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
15% protein 3.5% carbohydrate 30.3% lipid ¹⁷⁴	nd	β-carotene 0.02 fucoxanthin 5.40 (mg/g DW) ¹⁷³	C16:0 21.4% C16:1 25.1% C18:0 0.3% C18:1 0.5% C18:2 0.3% ¹⁷² C16:0 16% C16:1 60.7% C18:0 1.3% C18:1 2.7% C18:2 1.8% C18:3(n-6) 0.2% C20:4 2.4% C20:5 14.9% ¹⁷¹

26.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Navicula sp.* CCAP 1050/19, *N. salinicola* CCAP 1050/10, *N. perminuta* 1050/15, *N. glaciei* CCAP 1050/16, *N. directa* CCAP 1050/18
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Navicula sp.* RCC4611, 5169, 5170, 6032, *N. normaloides* RCC5230
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank

Strain(s) available: *Navicula* sp. BEA0524, *N. veneta* BEA0517B, *N. recens* BEA0387, *N. salinicola* BEA0053, 0054, 0055,

Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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27. *Nitzschia* sp.

A genus of diatoms found in a variety of habitats, including marine and freshwater environments. Some strains are characterised by their ability to produce the neurotoxin domoic acid, causing amnesic shellfish poisoning in humans ¹⁷⁵. They can grow phototrophically, heterotrophically or mixotrophically.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
UTEX 2047

27.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁷⁶ <i>obtained from Instituto de Ciencias Marinas de Andalucía in Cádiz</i>	System: 10L bags Medium: F/2 medium with 1 mg/L silicate Carbon source: nd Temperature: 28.5°C Light: 62 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous light	nd	nd	0.69x10 ⁶ cells/mL
<i>N. inconspicua</i> Grunow ¹⁷⁷	System: 2L conical flasks Medium: artificial seawater Carbon source: 5% CO ₂ , 0.1% acetate or glucose Temperature: nd Light: 42 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12:12h L:D	nd	nd	0.132 (acetate) 0.146 (glucose) 0.152 (CO ₂)
nd ¹⁷⁸ <i>isolated from central-western Ghats, India</i>	System: 0.5L Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: f/2 medium Carbon source: 7.5 g/L glucose, or none Temperature: 25°C Light: 60 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12:12h L:D, or none	nd	0.0071 (phototrophic) 0.0052 (heterotrophic) 0.0073 (mixotrophic)	0.127 (phototrophic) 0.095 (heterotrophic) 0.139 (mixotrophic)

<i>N. laevis</i> UTEX 2047 ¹⁷⁹	System: 0.5L Erlenmeyer flasks	nd	nd	0.50 (phototrophic)
	Medium: LDM medium			2.04 (heterotrophic)
	Carbon source: 5 g/L glucose, or none Temperature: 25°C Light: 60 µmol/m ² /s continuous illumination, or none			2.27 (mixotrophic)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

27.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
protein 14.5% carbohydrate 18.7% lipid 4.9% ash 62% ¹⁷⁶	C 29.7% N ----- O 47.1% Si 16.9% (phototrophic)	nd	C14:0 9.5% C15:0 2.75% C16:0 17.4% C16:1(n-7) 19.6% C16:2(n-6) 1.8% C18:0 1.2% C18:1(n-9) 3.1% C18:2(n-6) 4.1% C18:3(n-3) 1.7% C20:4(n-6) 5.7% C20:5(n-3) 16.6% C22:6(n-6) 1.7% ¹⁷⁶
protein 10.8-18.8% carbohydrate 3.0-14.0% lipid 12.5-20.5% ash 31.5-41.8% ¹⁷⁷	C 35.4% N 31.3% O 27.1% Si 4.24% (heterotrophic)		
	C 48.0% N ----- O 38.3% Si 8.11% (mixotrophic) ¹⁷⁸		

27.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *N. thermaloides* AC712
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nitzschia* sp. CCAP 1052/23, *N. ovalis* CCAP 1052/12, *N. epithemoides* CCAP 1052/18, *N. frigida* CCAP1052/24, *N. palea* CCAP 1052/25
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nitzschia* sp. RCC80, 457, 466, 469, 817, 826, 895, 2276, 2600, 2602, 2623, 2638, 2681, 2683, 2933, 2934, 2986, 2987, 2988, 2989, 2990, 4856, 5171, 5343, 5388, 5389, 5390, 5391, 5392, 5393, 5394, 5395, 5396, 5458, 5489, 5816, 7073, 7298, *N. Closterium* RCC81, *N. laevis* RCC7072, *N. logiwskii* RCC7302, *N. spathulata* RCC7645
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nitzschia* sp. BEA 0497, 0504B, 0526B, *N. palea* BEA 0166B, 0255B, 0256B, 0264B, 0262B, 0394, 0260B, *N. cf. pusilla* BEA 0261B, 0393B, *N. communis* BEA 0269, *N. ovalis* BEA 0423B, *N. cf. supralitorea* BEA 0498B, *N. cf. filiformis* BEA 0539B, *N. microcephala* BEA 0643B, *N. cf. ventricosa* BEA 1523B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:
 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, ***Nitzschia***, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis***Locations:** Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSS - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², ***Nitzschia* sp.**⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina (A. platensis)*, from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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28. *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*

A marine diatom strain with ability to produce high yields of fatty acids including polyunsaturated fatty acids, therefore leading to applications for animal feed, nutritional supplement, and biofuel ^{180,181}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1055/1, CCMP 632, PTN0301, CCMP 632.

28.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1055/1G ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: f/2 + Si medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.084	0.16	3.2
PTN0301 ¹⁸² <i>Isolated from water samples collected in the North Sea</i>	System: 1 L bottles Medium: modified f/2 medium, with air or CO ₂ supply Temperature: 20 \pm 1°C Light: 90-110 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	nd	nd	1.6 (with CO ₂) 1.0 (with air)
PTN0301 ¹⁸² <i>Isolated from water samples collected in the North Sea</i>	System: open ponds (1000 L) Medium: digestate from anaerobic digestion Temperature: outdoors Light: outdoors	0.041	nd	Between 0.3 and 0.8
CCMP 632 ¹⁸³	System: 1 L flasks (800 mL working volume) Medium: mixture of municipal wastewater (MW) and seawater (SW) Temperature: 20 \pm 1°C Light: 120 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.289 \pm 0.0001 (in MW:SW=2:1) 0.238 \pm 0.002 (in MW:SW=1:1)	1.04 \pm 0.01 (in MW:SW=2:1) 0.97 \pm 0.02 (in MW:SW=1:1)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

28.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
42% protein ³⁸ 12% lipid 39% carbohydrate --- <i>Growth on air</i> ¹⁸² 41.5±0.4% protein 26.7±0.0% lipid 9.5±2.3% polysaccharides <i>Growth on CO₂</i> ¹⁸² 33.5±1.0% protein 33.8±3.7% lipid 24.0±0.1% polysaccharides	nd	nd	C14:0 7.5% ³⁸ C16:0 12.6% C16:1 23.8% C16:2 4.1% C16:3 8.4% C16:4 2.9% C18:1 1.4% C18:2 2.1% C20:4 0.7% C20:5 30.2% other 6.3% --- C14:0, 6.55±0.32% ¹⁸² C16:0, 19.24±0.19% C16:3+C16:1, 49.41±2.68% C18:0, 0.74±0.10 % C86:2+C18:1, 3.63±0.25% C20:4, 1.15±0.12% C20:5, 17.77±2.23%

28.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. tricornutum* AC171, AC590, AC591
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. tricornutum* CCAP 1052/1A, 1052/1B, 1052/6, 1055/1 to 1055/9
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. tricornutum* IFREMER, Klaus 11b, Pt1_8.6, *Phaeodactylum* sp.
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPESCA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator

Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to) ^{153,154}:

- *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrans*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Location: Vigo, Spain

- **Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:

- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- **Name:** [Andalusian Center of Science and Marine Technology](#) (CACYTMAR) | [Instituto Universitario de Investigacion Marina](#) (INMAR) at University of Cádiz, Spain

Business/organisation: Higher education, research & development

Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, genomics, molecular biology, waste water treatment. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Botryococcus braunii* ⁹⁵, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁹⁶, [*Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella kessleri*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Scenedesmus obliquus*] ⁹⁷

Location: Cádiz, Spain

- **Name:** [ABIMS – Analysis and Bioinformatics for Marine Science](#)

Business/organisation: platform, informatics

Expertise: bioinformatics, database, metagenomics, molecular biology, software development, transcriptomics. Research outputs associated to the company, as listed in their publications page, include (but are not limited to):

- *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ¹⁸⁴, *Synechococcus* sp. ¹⁸⁵

Location: Roscoff, France

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MICROALGAE

- Name:** [Bantry Marine Research Station](#)

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, environment, nutraceuticals, ecophysiology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*¹⁸⁶

Location: Cork, Ireland

- Name:** [Department of Chemical and Biological Engineering, The University of Sheffield](#)

Network: [Algal Biotechnology Sheffield Network](#)

Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.

Expertise: Research outputs with microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus subspicatus*¹², *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*^{13,14}, *Dunaliella salina*^{13,15,16}, *Micractinium inermum*¹³, *Chlorella vulgaris*^{17,18}, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*^{19,20}, *Nannochloropsis salina*¹⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*²⁰

Location: Sheffield, UK

- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

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European Regional Development Fund

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Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁴³:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, and ***Phaeodactylum***

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

- **Name:** [Sparos](#)

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, ecophysiology, genomics. Research outputs associated to the company include (but are not limited to):

- ***Phaeodactylum tricornutum*** ¹⁴⁴, *Tetraselmis* sp. ¹⁴⁵, *Nannochloropsis oceanica* ¹⁴⁶

Location: Olhão, Portugal

- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: SME

Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:

- *Spirulina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Tetraselmis suecica*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, ***Phaeodactylum tricornutum***.

Location: Worcester, United Kingdom

- **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on ¹¹⁹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnoraphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., ***Phaeodactylum tricornutum***, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyl, Scotland

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Ochrophyta (Ochrophytes)

Previously classified with other heterokonts such as the pseudofungi, the heterokont algae are now sometimes classified within the phylum Ochrophyta¹⁸⁷. Members of Xanthophyceae and Eustigmatophyceae lack fucoxanthin and chlorophyll *b*, giving them a yellow-greenish colour. Eustigmatophytes also lack chlorophyll *c*, and have a coccoid morphology. Chrysophytes (golden microalgae) are able to grow both heterotrophically and autotrophically, and even phagotrophically, and several species can form harmful algal blooms¹.

Major classes

No. of species in Algaebase

Chrysophyceae	1265
Eustigmatophyceae	221
Dictyochophyceae	214
Phaeophyceae	2143
Xanthophyceae	623

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above

Class: Chrysophyceae

29. *Ochromonas* sp.

A unicellular flagellate belonging to the golden algae. It is found in freshwater environments and can grow phototrophically, heterotrophically and mixotrophically. Additionally, they can grow via phagotrophic metabolism, where they engulf smaller microorganisms in order to obtain nutrients ¹⁸⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
ATCC 30004

29.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁸⁹	System: 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: nd Carbon source: 10 g/L glucose Temperature: 15-30°C Light: 1500-2000 lux, continuous illumination	nd	nd	15°C – 1.2 ± 0.2 20°C – 5.8 ± 0.8 25°C – 4.0 ± 0.8 30°C – 3.6 ± 0.3
ATCC 30004 ¹⁹⁰	System: 3L fermentor Medium: chemically defined media ¹⁹¹ Carbon source: glycerol/acetic acid Temperature: 22°C Light: none	nd	nd	~22

<i>Ochromonas</i> sp. strain-01 ¹⁸⁸	System: 500 mL triangular flasks Medium: BG11 Carbon source: <i>M. aeruginosa</i> Temperature: 23°C Light: 25-28 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ in 16:8h L:D	nd	nd	4.6×10^6 cells mL^{-1} <i>(when cultivated with <i>M. aeruginosa</i>)</i> 3.4×10^6 cells mL^{-1} <i>(when cultivated alone)</i>
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

29.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
protein 104 ng/ μg carbohydrate 536 ng/ μg lipid 389 ng/ μg <i>(at 15°C)</i>	nd	Fucoxanthin content 11.58 mg/g 1.315 mg/L/day <i>(when cultivated with <i>M. aeruginosa</i>)</i>	lipid ~47% <i>(continuous addition of glycerol and acetic acid after 115 h)</i>
protein 404 ng/ μg carbohydrate 105 ng/ μg lipid 438 ng/ μg <i>(at 20°C)</i>		9.58 mg/g 0.494 mg/L/day <i>(when cultivated alone)</i> ¹⁸⁸	lipid ~75% <i>(continuous addition of glycerol (during 66 – 102 h) and acetic acid (during 71 – 143 h))</i> ¹⁹⁰
protein 305 ng/ μg carbohydrate 118 ng/ μg lipid 485 ng/ μg <i>(at 25°C)</i> ¹⁸⁹			

29.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. aestuarii* AC24, *O. distigma* AC25
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *O. tuberculata* CCAP 933/27
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Ochromonas* sp. RCC 480, 3643, 6719, 7027, *O. triangulata* RCC21
Location: Roscoff, France

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Class: Eustigmatophyceae

30. *Microchloropsis salina*

Formerly known as *Nannochloropsis salina*³³. It is a marine microalga widely used in aquaculture as it is rich in PUFA (particularly EPA), antioxidant pigment, and numerous bioactive compounds¹⁹².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
SAG 40.85, CCMP 1776.

30.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ¹⁹² <i>obtained from the culture collection of Cochin University of Science and Technology, India</i>	System: 250 mL conical flasks Medium: f/2 medium prepared in artificial seawater Temperature: 28±2°C Light: 27.02 μmol/m ² /s, L: D cycle nd	nd	nd	9.0x10 ⁶ cells/mL
SAG 40.85 ¹⁹³	System: 4 m ² (40 L) open thin-layer cascade reactor Medium: ASW medium Temperature and light: simulated conditions of Almería	nd	nd	15.4

nd ¹⁹⁴ <i>obtained from the Rajiv Gandhi Centre for Aquaculture, Marine Products Export Development Authority (MPEDA), Sirkali, Tamil Nadu, India</i>	System: Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: Walne medium Carbon source: glucose and sodium acetate (0.25, 0.5 and 1 g/L) Temperature: 27 °C Light: 3000 lux	nd	nd	1.795
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30.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
~20% protein ¹⁹² ~15% lipid ~10% carbohydrate --- 48% protein ¹⁹³ 16% lipid 26% carbohydrate <i>(in nutrient replete medium)</i> 12% protein 46% lipid 35% carbohydrate <i>(in nitrogen-limited medium)</i> --- 45% lipid ¹⁹⁴ <i>(in heterotrophic conditions)</i>	nd	~800 µg/L chlorophyll ¹⁹² ~850 µg/L total carotenoids	C14:0 6.5% ¹⁹³ C16:0 22.0% C16:1 31.3% C18:0 0.4% C18:1 4.8% C18:1 0.4% C18:2 1.6% C18:3 0.1% C20:0 0.1% C20:1 0.1% C20:2 0.1% C20:4 4.0% C20:3 0.1% C20:5 28.3% <i>(in nutrient replete medium)</i> C14:0 3.4% C16:0 48.6% C16:1 30.1% C18:0 1.2 % C18:1 6.6 % C18:1 0.4 % C18:2 1.3 % C18:3 0.4 % C20:0 0.1 % C20:1 0.1 % C20:2 0.1 % C20:4 2.1 % C20:3 0.1 % C20:5 5.5 % <i>(in nitrogen-limited medium)</i>

30.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *M. salina* CCAP 849/2, 849/3, 849/4
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

- **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *M. salina* CCMP527
Location: Roscoff, France

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31. *Nannochloropsis oculata*

A eukaryotic marine strain of the Eustigmatophyceae class with applications for nutritional supplement, and biofuel, particularly due to its fatty acid characteristics. It can be cultivated autotrophically in photobioreactor or open pond conditions, with a stress induction such as nitrogen starvation, typically used to induce higher fatty acid yields^{195,196}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 849/1

31.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 849/1 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: F2 (f/2) medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.09	0.32	2.5
nd ⁵¹ <i>obtained from NLP corp (Busan, Korea)</i>	System: PBR (5L, 3 L working volume) Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 108.9 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 12h L: 12h D	nd	0.0475	0.51
nd ¹⁹⁷ <i>obtained from the Fisheries Research Institute (Pingtung, Taiwan)</i>	System: 3 L PBR Two stages: 1 st N replete, 2 nd N deplete Medium: Basal medium with 35 g/L salinity Temperature: 25°C Light: 300, 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous	nd	nd	3.36 (at 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 3.44 (at 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

31.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
40% protein ³⁸ 33% lipid 10% carbohydrate --- ~30% lipids in two-stage system ⁵¹ --- 43.2% lipid ¹⁹⁷ (at 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$) 44.5% lipid (at 500 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	55% C ³⁸ 3% N C/N ratio 21	nd	C14:0 7.2% ³⁸ C16:0 23.4% C16:1 26.9% C16:3 0.5% C18:1 13.2% C18:2 1.2% C20:4 2.7% C20:5 14.3% other 10.1% --- C14:0 4.13% ¹²⁶ C16:0 20.70% C16:1 17.12% C16:2 3.88% C16:3 5.35% C18:0 0.98% C18:1 7.46% C18:2 8.75% C18:3 10.08% C20:4 2.88% C20:5 18.67% $\Sigma\text{SFA}=25.8$ $\Sigma\text{MUFA}=24.58$ $\Sigma\text{PUFA}=49.62$ --- $\Sigma\text{SFA}=34.15\text{-}40.15\%$ ¹⁹⁷ $\Sigma\text{PUFA}=29.96\text{-}44.54\%$

31.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *N. oculata* AC225, ACAC227
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *N. oculata* CCAP 849/1, CCAP 849/7
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK

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- Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*⁹¹, *Arthrospira maxima*⁹², ***Nannochloropsis* spp.**⁹³, *Micractinum inermum*¹⁴, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{42,43}, *Nosctoc sp.*, *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK

- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of⁸⁶:

 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, ***Nannochloropsis***

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

- Name:** [Buggypower](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organization type: producer, research & development, downstream processing
Expertise: feed, food, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company specialises in¹²⁷:

 - *Chlorella*, ***Nannochloropsis***, *Rhodomonas*

Location: Lisbon, Portugal (shared services centre & Alguimya store); Funchal, Portugal (Financial office); Porto Santo, Portugal (Buggypower production unit in partnership with Electricity Company of Madeira); San Pedro del Pinatar, Spain (Financial office); Lorqui, Spain (Research and development pilot plant)

- Name:** [Laboratoire GENie des Procédés Environnement – Agroalimentaire, GEPEA](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, higher education
Expertise: bioenergy, biotechnology, chemistry, engineering. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Chlorella vulgaris*¹¹⁶, *Chlorella sorokiniana*¹¹⁷, *Parachlorella kessleri*¹¹⁸, ***Nannochloropsis oculata***¹¹⁶

Location: Saint-Nazaire, France

- Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton
Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from ¹⁴³:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.

Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner

Business/organisation type: SME

Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:

- *Spirulina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Nannochloropsis sp.*, *Tetraselmis suecica*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.

Location: Worcester, United Kingdom

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Euglenophyta (Euglenoids)

Euglenoids are common marine and freshwater flagellates, closely related to the parasitic trypanosomes. They are unique in their production of the storage carbohydrate paramylon and their proteinaceous, ribbon-like surface structure ¹⁴⁹.

Major classes

No. of species in Algaebase

Euglenophyceae	995
Kinetoplastea	416
Peranemea	330
Stavomonadea	150

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above

Class: Euglenophyceae

32. *Euglena gracilis*

A unicellular phototrophic freshwater microalga. It can grow under phototrophic, heterotrophic and mixotrophic conditions. *E. gracilis* synthesises relevant bioproducts at a commercial level such as protein containing essential amino acids, pro(vitamins), lipids, and the b-1,3-glucan paramylon ¹⁹⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
NIES-48

32.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
NIES-48 ¹⁹⁹	System: 2.5 L glass vessel bioreactors Medium: Chemically defined medium Carbon source: 1.8% CO ₂ enriched air (for phototrophic growth); glucose (for mixotrophic and heterotrophic growth) Temperature: 23, 27, 30°C Light: 400 μmol/m ² /s (for phototrophic growth) and dark conditions (for heterotrophic growth)	nd	nd	5 (in phototrophic cultures with high light and 23°C) 10.5 (in mixotrophic cultures at 27°C)

nd ²⁰⁰ (obtained from the Culture Collection Centre of the Institute of Applied Microbiology, University of Tokyo, Japan)	System: 500 mL erlenmeyer flasks and airlift photobioreactor Medium: BG11 medium and different NPKs Temperature: 25°C±1 Light: 2570 Lux, L:D cycle: continuous light illumination	nd	nd	26.0 ×10 ⁷ cell/mL (in flasks) 228.8 ×10 ⁷ cell/mL (in airlift PBR)
NIES-48 ²⁰¹	System: 15 L polycarbonate culture vessel Medium: municipal wastewater Temperature: 28±1°C Light: 80 µmol/m ² /s, 16 L: 8 D cycle	nd	0.087 (in a co-culture with bacteria containing 8×10 ⁶ CFU/mL)	0.7

^o Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

32.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
12-34% protein ¹⁹⁹ 22% lipid ---	nd	6 µg/mL chlorophyll a+b ^j (in co-culture with bacteria)	20:5(n-3) EPA 0.48% ¹⁹⁹ 22:6(n-3) DHA 0.38%
33.3% protein ²⁰⁰ 16.4% lipid ---			
30.9% lipid ²⁰¹			

32.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *E. gracilis* CCAP 1224/38, 1224/5Y, 1224/5Z, *Euglena* sp. CCAP 1224/47
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Euglena* sp. BEA 0201B, 0799, 0202B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

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Cryptophyta (Cryptomonads)

Cryptomonads are flagellates found in freshwater and marine habitats. They contain chloroplast phycobiliproteins similar to the red algae, and possess the same type I purple bacterial form of Rubisco as that found in red algae ²⁰². Members of Cryptophyceae are among the more productive flagellates found in aquatic environments, and have a high content of polyunsaturated fatty acids ²⁰³.

Major classes

No. of species in Algaebase

Cryptophyceae	217
Goniomonadophyceae	14
Katablepharidophyceae	11

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above

Class: Cryptophyceae

33. *Rhodomonas* sp.

A flagellate unicellular red alga belonging to the class Cryptophyceae with cell size between 9.2 and 9.9 μm . This marine microalga plays a significant role as live food in aquaculture due to its protein, EPA and DHA content ²⁰⁴. Also a source of phycoerythrin.

Commonly cultivated species and strains include:

Rhodomonas sp. (strain Hf-1)

R. salina (strains CCAP 978/27, CCMP 1319, CS-174, CS-24)

R. lens (strain CMP 739)

33.1 Cultivation characteristics of *Rhodomonas* sp.

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
Hf-1 ²⁰⁴	<p>System: 200 mL Erlenmeyer flasks</p> <p>Medium: f/2 medium, salinity of 28 psu.</p> <p>Temperature: 20°C</p> <p>Light: 35 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light.</p>	nd	nd	<p>4.36\pm0.20 x 10⁶ cell/mL (temperature, 24°C)</p> <p>3.74\pm0.28 x 10⁶ cell/mL (salinity, 21 psu)</p> <p>3.60\pm0.49 x 10⁶ cell/mL (light intensity 80 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)</p> <p>4.57$\pm$0.22 x 10⁶ cell/mL (light colour, White)</p>
nd ²⁰⁵ from the Dutch aquaculture industry	<p>System: Flat-panel PBR</p> <p>Medium: ASW medium</p> <p>Temperature: (15–20–25–30°C)</p> <p>Light: 60–195–330–495–600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light.</p>	nd	1.4 (25°C, 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)	11.25 x 10 ⁶ cell/mL (25°C, 600 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$)

nd ²⁰⁶ isolated from coastal waters in north-eastern Brazil (state of Paraiba).	System: 500 mL Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: f/2 medium, salinity of 34 psu. Temperature: 21± 2°C Light: 50 µmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D.	nd	nd	11.3 x 10 ⁵ cell/mL (N-sufficient medium) 5.0 x 10 ⁵ cell/mL (N-starved medium)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

33.2 Biomass characteristics of *Rhodomonas* sp.

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Protein: ²⁰⁶ ~ 30 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) ~ 25 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-starved medium) Carbohydrates: ~ 25 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) ~ 150 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-starved medium)	nd	Chlorophyll a: ²⁰⁶ ~ 1.3µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) Chlorophyll c: ~ 1.1 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium) Phycoerythrin: ~ 5.5 µg/10 ⁶ cell (N-sufficient medium)	Σ SFA 13-16% ²⁰⁵ Σ MUFA 3-7% Σ PUFA (excl. EPA + DHA) 47-56% Σ EPA + DHA 11-22%

33.3 Cultivation characteristics of *R. salina*

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ²⁰⁷	System: 200 mL Erlenmeyer flasks. Continuous culture (unknown dilution rate), seawater Medium: Conway medium Temperature: 20°C Light: cool white fluorescents, 1,500 lux, continuous light Aeration: mixture air: CO ₂ =98.5:1.5%	nd	nd	nd

CS-24 and CS-174 ²⁰⁸	<p>System: 1-L Erlenmeyer flasks. Batch mode</p> <p>Medium: Modified f/2 medium: 0.441 or 3.529 mM N, 0.018 or 0.144 mM P; salinity 33 psu</p> <p>Temperature: 19±1 °C and 29±1 °C</p> <p>Light: 100 or 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous irradiance</p>	nd	<p>CS-24: 0.07 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 or 29 °C)</p> <p>CS-174: 0.105 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p>	<p>CS-24: 3.2 x 10⁶ cell/mL and 0.7 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 or 29 °C)</p> <p>CS-174: 4.7 x 10⁶ cell/mL and 1.05 g dry weight/L (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P; 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p>
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

33.4 Biomass characteristics of *R. salina*

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
<p>Total sterol content ²⁰⁷ 55.68 fg/cell Cholesterol 9.71% Brassicasterol 90.29%</p> <p>---</p>			<p>Total fatty acids ²⁰⁷: 11.34 pg/cell Σ SFA 37.11% Σ MUFA 15.61% Σ PUFA 46.77% EPA 4.78% DHA 3.58%</p> <p>---</p>
<p>Protein ²⁰⁹: CS-24 and CS-174 Max. ~ 55% d.w. (3.529 mM N, 0.144 mM P) Min. ~ 35% d.w. (0.441 mM N, 0.018 mM P)</p> <p>Lipids ²⁰⁹: Max. CS-24 ~ 18% d.w. Max. CS-174 ~ 25% d.w. (0.441 mM N, 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Min. CS-24 ~ 5% d.w. Min. CS-174 ~ 6% d.w. (0.441 mM N, 0.018 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 29 °C)</p>	nd	nd	<p>CS-24 ²⁰⁹: Max. Σ SFA ~ 42% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 29 °C)</p> <p>Max. Σ MUFA ~ 27% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. Σ PUFA 55% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. EPA 10% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. DHA 6.4%</p>

			<p>(3.529 mM N & 0.018 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>CS-174 ²⁰⁹: Max. Σ SFA ~ 47% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 29 °C)</p> <p>Max. Σ MUFA ~ 26% (3.529 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 100 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. Σ PUFA 55% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. EPA 13.2% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p> <p>Max. DHA 6.5% (0.441 mM N & 0.144 mM P, 200 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 19 °C)</p>
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33.5 Cultivation characteristics of *R. lens*

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP 739 ⁷⁷	<p>System: 80-mL, 30-mm diameter glass tubes. Semi-continuous culture (10%-20%-30%-40%-50% daily dilution rate)</p> <p>Medium: Algal-1 ²¹⁰, salinity 35 psu</p> <p>Temperature: 21±1.5°C</p> <p>Light: cool white fluorescents, 242 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, light:dark cycle of 12 h:12 h</p> <p>Aeration: mixture air:CO₂</p>	nd	0.38 g d.w./L/d (40 % dilution rate)	<p>Max: 22.16 × 10⁶ cells/mL, (10% dilution rate)</p> <p>Min. 7.17 × 10⁶ cells/mL (50% dilution rate)</p>

CCMP 739 ²¹¹	System: 4-L Erlenmeyer flasks or 10-L polycarbonate carboys. Medium: f/2 medium; salinity 34-35 psu Temperature: room temperature, 22-29 °C Light: natural sunlight	nd	nd	nd
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

33.6 Biomass characteristics of *R. lens*

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
Protein ⁷⁷ : Max. 64 pg/cell, 45% of organic fraction (40% dilution rate) Min. 36 pg/cell, 64% of organic fraction (10% dilution rate) Lipids ⁷⁷ : Max. ~ 42% of organic fraction (10% dilution rate) Min. ~ 20% of organic fraction (30%-40% dilution rate)	nd	Total chlorophylls ⁷⁷ : 1.4-2.0 pg/cell (50% and 40% dilution rate, respectively) Phycoerythrin ⁷⁷ : 3.4-8.5 pg/cell (10% and 50% dilution rate, respectively)	Σ SFA max. 54% ⁷⁷ (10% dilution rate) Σ MUFA max. 8% (10% dilution rate) Σ PUFA max. 65% (20%-40% dilution rate) EPA max. 9% (20% dilution rate) DHA max. 4% (20% dilution rate) --- Σ SFA ~ 22.2% ²¹¹ Σ MUFA ~ 12.3% Σ PUFA ~ 65.5% EPA 11.9% DHA 7.4%

33.7 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Rhodomonas* sp. AC162
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

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- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *R. salina* CCAP 978/27, *R. maculata* CCAP 979/14, *R. atrorosea* CCAP 978/6A, 978/6B, *R. baltica* CCAP 979/9, *R. chrysoidea* CCAP 978/6
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Rhodomonas* sp. (various), *R. salina* CCMP322, AC721, AC160
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Rhodomonas* sp. BEA 0081B, 0223B, 0113, 0113B, 0116B, 0117B, 0121B, 0124, 0689B, 0125B,
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPECA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator
Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to) ^{153,154}:
 - *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrans*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, ***Rhodomonas lens***, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochrysis lutea*
ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Vigo, Spain
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:
 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, ***Rhodomonas***, *Nannochloropsis***Locations:** Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

- Name:** [Buggypower](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner
Business/organization type: producer, research & development, downstream processing
Expertise: feed, food, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company specialises in ¹²⁷:
 - *Chlorella*, *Nannochloropsis*, ***Rhodomonas***

Location: Lisbon, Portugal (shared services centre & Alguimya store); Funchal, Portugal (Financial office); Porto Santo, Portugal (Buggypower production unit in partnership with Electricity Company of Madeira); San Pedro del Pinatar, Spain (Financial office); Lorqui, Spain (Research and development pilot plant)
- Name:** [Group of Biotechnology and Aquaculture](#), Universidad de Santiago de Compostela
Business/organization type: research & development, higher education
Expertise: biotechnology, aquaculture. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - [*Dunaliella salina*, *Dunaliella tertiolecta*] ⁵⁰, *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁵⁶, [*Tetraselmis suecica*, *Tetraselmis* sp.] ⁵⁷, ***Rhodomonas lens*** ⁷⁷

Location: Santiago de Compostela, A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigelowiella natans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus like* ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium baillyanum* ⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa* ^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium* ⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina* ^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp. ⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta* ^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi* ⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis* ⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra* ⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana* ⁶², *Nitzschia* sp. ⁶², *Odontella aurita* ⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri* ⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*) ^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea* ⁶², ***Rhodomonas salina*** ^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus* ⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus* ⁶², *Skeletonema grethae* ⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica* ⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana* ⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea* ⁷¹, *Euglena proxima* ⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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Haptophyta (Haptophytes)

Haptophytes are photosynthetic algae that contain a haptonema, a microtubule-supported appendage lying between two flagella. They are mostly marine, and are abundant even at greater water depths. They are divided into two classes. Of these, the Coccolithophyceae form the larger group. They contain a cell coat of coccoliths composed of calcite. Haptophyte algae are considered high-quality foods for the aquaculture industry, although some species may produce toxins ¹⁴⁹.

Major classes

Coccolithophyceae

Pavlovophyceae

No. of species in Algaebase

1545

15

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above.

Class: Coccolithophyceae

34. *Isochrysis galbana*

A eukaryotic marine microalga which is a species of Haptophyta. For its good nutritive characteristics (especially in relation to polyunsaturated fatty-acid composition), is of substantial interest in aquaculture ²¹². It is also investigated for its high amount of fucoxanthin ²¹³.

34.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ²¹⁴ <i>from Marine Microalgae Research Center, Ocean University of China</i>	System: Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: f/2 Temperature: 23°C Light: 4.0 mW/cm ² , 16 h L: 8 h D	nd	nd	1.69x10 ⁷ cells/mL (500 μmol/L phosphorous)
nd ²¹⁵ <i>Aquatic Research Laboratory at Isfahan University of Technology, Isfahan, Iran</i>	System: 10 L carboys Medium: Walne's medium Temperature: 25°C Light: 80 mmol photons/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	nd	nd	1.55x10 ⁷ cells/mL (144mg/L nitrogen)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

34.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
30% protein ²¹⁴ 33% carbohydrate (100 µmol/L phosphorous) ---	nd	3.24% chlorophyll ²¹⁴ (100 µmol/L phosphorous) ---	C14:0 26.34% ²¹⁵ C16:0 43.46% C16:1 1.4% C18:1n-7 17.25% C18:3n-3 3.52%
36.3% protein ²¹⁵ (36 mg/L nitrogen)		1.21 mg/L total carotenoid ²¹⁵ (72 mg/L nitrogen)	C20:0 4.42% C20:3n-3 2.03% (0 mg/L nitrogen)
47% carbohydrate (0 mg/L nitrogen)			
30.6% lipids (144 mg/L nitrogen)			

34.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *I. galbana* CCAP 927/1, 927/20, 941/3, 949/1
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *I. galbana* AC101 (not distributed), AC34, AC80, PLY240, PLY507, PLY8, GE_FL_IC_SingleCell_103, GE_FL_IC_SingleCell_104, GE_DV_IC_DIL_194
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [AlgoSource](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ⁹⁴:
 - *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*
Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

- Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPECA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator
Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to) ^{153,154}:

 - *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), ***Isochrysis galbana***, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Pavlova gyrans*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochyrysis lutea*

ANFACO-CECOPECA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Vigo, Spain
- Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁹¹, *Arthrospira maxima* ⁹², *Nannochloropsis* spp. ⁹³, *Micractinium inermum* ¹⁴, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{42,43}, *Nosctoc* sp., ***Isochrysis galbana*** and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:

 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, ***Isochrysis***, *Pavlova*, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Alexandrium minutum* ⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense* ⁶², *Bigelowiella natans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum* ⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis* ⁶², *Chaetoceros minus* ⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri* ⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like ⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica* ⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans* ⁶², *Closterium*

*baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, ***Isochrysis galbana***⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of **Spirulina**-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture⁷². Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from⁷³:

- *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, ***Isochrysis galbana***, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*⁷³

Locations: Asturias, Spain

- **Name:** [PhytoBloom](#)/Necton

Business/organisation: producer, research and development

Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. Their line of products include culture media for microalgae, and aquaculture food concentrates from²¹⁶:

- *Nannochloropsis*, *Tetraselmis*, ***Isochrysis***, and *Phaeodactylum*

Location: Olhão and Algarve, Portugal

- **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., ***Isochrysis galbana***, *Limnoraphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyl, Scotland

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35. *Tisochrysis lutea*

A marine flagellate microalga extensively used as a feed stock in aquaculture and commonly known as T-iso. It is genetically distinct from *Isochrysis galbana*, despite seemingly being morphologically identical²¹⁷. *T. lutea* has been recognized as one of the most suitable species for DHA production due to its fast growth and high DHA content (12–14%)²¹⁸. It is also obtaining increased interest for fucoxanthin production²¹⁸.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCMP1324.

35.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP1324 ²¹⁸	<p>System: 500-mL Erlenmeyer flask (<i>in experimental setup 1</i>); 1-L bioreactor (<i>in experimental setup 2</i>)</p> <p>Medium: f/2-Si medium</p> <p>Carbon source: glucose, glycerol, and sodium acetate (<i>in experimental setup 1</i>)</p> <p>Temperature: 23°C</p> <p>Light: 3000 lux, 14h L: 10h D cycle</p>	nd	0.02 (growing mixotrophically with glycerol as source of carbon)	1.4 (growing mixotrophically)
nd ²¹⁹ <i>obtained from NECTON, S.A. (Olhão, Portugal)</i>	<p>System: flat panel photobioreactors</p> <p>Medium: commercial culture medium stock NutriBloom Plus</p> <p>Temperature: 16.5, 20, 25, and 30 °C.</p> <p>Light: 50, 150, 300, and 500 μmol/m²/s, 18h L: 6h D cycle</p>	nd	0.35 (at 300 μmol/m ² /s) 0.42 (at 30 °C)	1.91 (at 300 μmol/m ² /s) 1.81 (at 30 °C)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

35.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
36.7% protein ²²⁰ 22.0% lipid 9.4% carbohydrate (<i>phototrophy</i>)	C/N ratio 92.5 ²¹⁸	16.39 mg/g ²¹⁹ fucoxanthin (50 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, dilution rate 0.47 d^{-1} , 30 °C)	C13:0 0.64–0.80% ²¹⁸ C14:0 14.13–17.75% C15:0 0.22–0.39% C16:0 10.17–13.44% C16:1 4.78–11.24% C17:0 0.80–0.92% C18:0 0.30–0.97%
41.7% protein 19.3% lipid 7.5% carbohydrate (<i>mixotrophy</i>)		7.8 mg/g chlorophyll-a ²²⁰ 4.8 mg/g carotenoids (<i>phototrophy</i>)	C18:1 12.54–13.36% C18:2 9.10–12.28% C18:3 4.86–10.39% C18:4 12.88–14.5% C20:0 0.24–3.07% C22:6 9.37– 13.77%
		18.9 mg/g chlorophyll-a ²²⁰ 4.8 mg/g carotenoids (<i>mixotrophy</i>)	

35.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. lutea* AC102, AC620
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. lutea* CCAP 927/14, 927/19,
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *T. lutea* Poulet, Caen, T-iso, AC620, AC102, CCMP463, PLY506A, PLY506B, PLY506C, PLY562
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Laboratoire Phycotoxines IFREMER](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, environmental monitoring
Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Tisochrysis lutea* ²²¹, *Microcystis aeruginosa* ²²²

The research team at IFREMER works in close collaboration with the EnhanceMicroAlgae team at [LIENSs, University of La Rochelle](#), France.

Location: Nantes, France

- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

- *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliania huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², ***Tisochrysis lutea***⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on¹¹⁹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, *Synechocystis* sp., ***T-isochrysis lutea***

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyl, Scotland

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Class: Pavlovophyceae

36. *Pavlova* sp.

A genus of haptophytes commonly employed as feed in aquaculture, *Pavlova* sp. are considered valuable producers of fucoxanthin and polyunsaturated fatty acids. They can grow heterotrophically, phototrophically and mixotrophically ^{223,224}.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCMP 459, OPMS 30543, RCC 1539, NBRC 102807, NBRC 102808, CS-182, CS-49 ^{223,225}

36.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP 459 ²²⁶	System: 1,250L PBR Medium: seawater and f/2 Carbon source: CO ₂ Temperature: 20°C Light: 208-585 μmol/m ² /s, continuous	nd	0.004	0.286
OPMS 30543 ²²³ <i>Isolated from Okinawa Main Island, Japan</i>	System: acrylic pipe PBR (60 mm outer diameter) Medium: 50% seawater and 2x Daigo's IMK Carbon source: air at 0.25 mL/min Temperature: nd Light: natural sunlight	nd	0.23	2.20
<i>P. pinguis</i> RCC 1539 ²²⁷	System: 1L flasks Medium: f/2-Si medium Carbon source: air Temperature: 25°C Light: 70 μmol/m ² /s in 16:8h L:D	nd	nd	0.368

<i>P. lutheri</i> CS-182 ²²⁵	System: 2L Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: seawater with f/2 medium Carbon source: air at 0.4 L/min Temperature: 22°C Light: 100 µmol/m ² /s in 12:12h L:D	nd	14 mg/L/day	125 pg/mL (<i>exponential</i>) 220 pg/mL (<i>stationary</i>)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

36.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
66.5% protein 6.7% carbohydrate 16.6% lipid ²²⁶	Calcium 0.40 Iron 0.73 Magnesium 0.43 Phosphorous 1.45 Potassium 1.73 Sodium 1.62 (mg/kg DW) ²²⁶	α-carotene 21.0 β-carotene 52.6 chlorophyll 894.2 fucoxanthin 367.5 lutein 162.4 phaeophytin 1.8 (mg/100g DW) ²²⁶	C14:0 22.9% C16:0 14.6% C16:1(n-7) 5.5% C18:3(n-3) 2.6% C18:4(n-3) 6.2% C20:5(n-3) 21.6% C22:5(n-6) 4.3% C22:6(n-3) 6.1% ²²⁶
25% protein 7% carbohydrate 8% lipid ²²⁵		fucoxanthin 20.86 mg/g DW 4.88 mg/L/day ²²³	
26% protein 7.4% carbohydrate 12% lipid ²²⁸			

36.3 Stakeholders in Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Pavlova* sp. AC33, AC87, AC248, AC251, *P. pinguis* AC19, AC96, AC696, *P. gyrans* AC28, AC98
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Pavlova* sp. CCAP 940/2, 940/3, *P. gyrans* CCAP 940/1B, 940/1C
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Pavlova* sp. RCC437, 441, 1530, 1531, 1533, 1538, 1540, 1548, 1554, 2541, 2550, 2551, 3458, 4098, 4120, 4496, 4497, 5622, 5624, 5625, 5626, 5627, 5628, 5629, 5945, 5946, 6257, 6431, 6852, *P. gyrans* RCC1524, 1526, 1545, 1553, *P. pinguis* RCC1539, 1552, 6260, *P. granifera* RCC1557
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Algal BioSciences – National University of Ireland](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Porphyridium purpureum*²²⁹, ***Pavlova lutheri***²³⁰
Location: Galway, Ireland
- Name:** [ANFACO-CECOPESCA](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae project Lead Coordinator
Business/organisation type: Marketing, research & development and innovation support in food and marine technology.
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology, marketing, valorisation and functionality of microalgal compounds. Microalgal expertise includes (not limited to)^{153,154}:
 - *Chaetoceros calcitrans*, *C. salsugineus*, *Conticribra weissflogii* (synonym of *Thalassiosira weissflogii*), *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, ***Pavlova gyrans***, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Rhodomonas lens*, *Tetraselmis chuii*, *Tisochyrysis lutea*
 ANFACO-CECOPESCA offers production of tailor-made microalgal biomass. Read more in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Vigo, Spain
- Name:** [Aqualgae](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of⁸⁶:
 - *Chlorella*, *Haematococcus*, *Arthrospira*, *Tetraselmis*, *Isochrysis*, ***Pavlova***, *Chaetoceros*, *Skeletonema*, *Nitzschia*, *Rhodomonas*, *Nannochloropsis*
Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

Class: Dinophyceae

37. *Amphidinium carterae*

A dinophyte strain well known to cause ciguatera fish poisoning (CFP) in human beings. It has been reported from several tropical and subtropical waters but never from the northern Arabian Sea bordering Pakistan.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
Dn241EHU, ACRN03

37.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
Dn241EHU 231,232	System: raceway PBR Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 21±1°C Light: 300-900 μE/m ² /s, L:D nd	nd	nd	nd
ACRN03 ^{231,233}	System: flask Medium: modified K medium Temperature: 21±1°C Light: 60 μE, 12 h L : 12 h D	nd	nd	nd
Dn241EHU 234,235	System: raceway PBR Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 21±1°C Light: mean value of 573 μE/m ² /s 24 h L : 0 h D	nd	25.8·10 ⁴ cells/mL/d ²³⁵	nd

nd ²³⁶	System: 1 L conical Erlenmeyer flasks Medium: Walne's nutrient formula Carbon source: air/CO ₂ Temperature: 20-22°C Light: 2000-8000 lux, 16 h L : 8 h D	nd	0.143-0.189 in low light 0.232-0.302 in high light	(0.65-1.4)·10 ⁶ cells/mL in low light 1.19 g/L in high light
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

37.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
30.9±0.3 % lipid 25.9±0.3 % protein 35.6±0.2 % carbohydrate 7.3±0.2 % ashes ²³¹			45.1 % neutral lipids 47.3 % glucolipids 7.6 % phospholipids ²³¹
23.5±0.5 % lipid 20.9±0.2 % protein 46.3±0.2 % carbohydrate 7.8±0.2 % ashes ²³¹	48.8±0.2 C% 33.8±0.3 O% 7.5±0.1 H% 5.2±0.1 N% 1.0±0.1 S% 3.2±0.1 P% ²³⁵	nd	47.33±2.37 % glycolipids 7.63±0.38 % phospholipids 45.06±2.25 % non-polar lipids ²³⁴
13.53 ± 0.45 % lipid ²³⁴			
3.26 ± 0.29% pigment 13.0±0.9% lipid ²³⁵			

37.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. carterae* AC208, AC792, AC793
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. carterae* CCAP 1102/1, 1102/2, 1102/3, 1102/4, 1102/5, 1102/7,
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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- **Name:** [Microalgae Culture Collection of the Plant Biology and Ecology Department at the University of the Basque Country](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Strain(s) available: *A. carterae* Dn241EHU
Location: Basque Country, Spain
- **Name:** [Culture Collection of Harmful Microalgae at the IEO](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Strain(s) available: *A. carterae* ACRN03
Location: Corazon de Maria, Spain
- **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. carterae* BEA 01119B, BEA 0624B, BEA 1367B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- **Name:** [Bigelow NCMA](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. carterae* CCMP3177
Location: East Boothbay Barcelona, US

38. *Alexandrium minutum*

A toxic dinoflagellate that may be responsible for paralytic shellfish poisoning (PSP) outbreaks throughout the world.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
AmKB06, AMTW, AMAD06 (CS-323), AMAD16 (CS-324), CCAP 1119/48, CCAP 1119/49, CCAP 1119/50

38.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
AmKB06 ²³⁷	System: 200 mL batch Medium: ES-DK medium Temperature: 25±0.5°C Light: 140 µmol/m ² /s, 15 h L: 9 h D	1.3·10 ³ -6.8·10 ³ cells/mL	nd	nd
AMTW ²³⁸	System: 250 mL conical flask Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20-25°C Light: 4.5-5.5 klx, L:D cycle N/A	nd	nd	6.29·10 ⁶ cells/mL (out-incubator)
AMTW ²³⁸	System: 500 mL beaker Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 6.5 klx, L:D cycle N/A	nd	nd	7.28·10 ⁶ cells/mL (incubator)
AMTW ²³⁸	System: 20 L jar Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20-25°C Light: 4.5-5.5 klx, L:D cycle N/A	nd	nd	2.82·10 ⁶ cells/mL (out-incubator)
AMAD06 ²³⁹	System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flask Medium: GSe medium Temperature: 18°C Light: 3000 µmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	2.4·10 ³ cells/mL/d	0.26/d	7.2·10 ⁴ cells/mL

AMAD06 ²³⁹	System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flask Medium: GSe medium Carbon source: 27 mL L ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ with air / CO ₂ Temperature: 18°C Light: 3000 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	4.6·10 ³ cells/mL/d	0.35/d	9.4·10 ⁴ cells/mL
AMAD16 ²³⁹	System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flask Medium: GSe medium Temperature: 18°C Light: 3000 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	1.8·10 ³ cells/mL/d	0.28/d	5.6·10 ⁴ cells/mL
AMAD16 ²³⁹	System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flask Medium: GSe medium Carbon source: 27 mL L ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ with air / CO ₂ Temperature: 18°C Light: 3000 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	4.8·10 ³ cells/mL/d	0.37/d	9.9·10 ⁴ cells/mL
AMAD06, AMAD16 ²³⁹	System: 2 L Erlenmeyer flask Medium: GSe medium Carbon source: 67 mL L ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ with air / CO ₂ Temperature: 18°C Light: 3000 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	6.5·10 ³ cells/mL/d from day 3 to day 17; 21.4·10 ³ cells/mL/d from day 17 to day 30	0.25-0.27/d	(3.9-4.8)·10 ⁵ cells/mL
AMAD06, AMAD16 ²³⁹	System: Photobioreactor Medium: GSe medium Carbon source: 200 mL L ⁻¹ min ⁻¹ with air / CO ₂ Temperature: 18°C Light: 100 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L : 12 h D	1.4·10 ⁴ cells/mL/d from day 3 to day 17	0.22/d	3.3·10 ⁵ cells/mL

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

38.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Toxin composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
nd	70-95% GTX1 & GTX4 ²³³ --- 60.21-67.09% GTX1 4.15- 8.7% GTX2 2.81-3.76% GTX3 25.95-27.33% GTX4 ₂₃₄ --- 38.1±10.8 % GTX1 0.77±1.49 % GTX2 2.82±8.16 % GTX3 58.3±9.40 % GTX4 _{234,235}	nd	nd

38.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. minutum* AC194
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. minutum* CCAP 1119/15, 1119/48, 1119/49, 1119/50
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Bigelow NCMA](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. minutum* CCMP113
Location: East Boothbay Barcelona, US

39. *Crypthecodinium cohnii*

A heterotrophic non-photosynthetic species of dinoflagellate microalgae industrially used in the production of docosahexaenoic acid. DHA fraction can reach 30-50% of the total lipid content ²⁴⁰.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
ATCC 30555, ATCC 30556, ATCC 30772.

39.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
ATCC 30555 ²⁴⁰	System: 1 L fermenters Medium: optimized experimental medium Temperature: 27°C	nd	nd	25.3
ATCC 30556 ²⁴¹	System: 250-ml Erlenmeyer flask and 5-L laboratory bioreactors Medium: standard medium (9 g/L glucose, 2 g/L yeast extract, 27.8 g/L sea salt) Temperature: 25°C Light: dark conditions	nd	nd	42 (under combined stress cultivation of temperature and nitrogen depletion)
M-1-2 ²⁴² (a mutant of <i>C. cohnii</i> ATCC 30556)	System: 5-L fermenter Medium: basal medium (25 g/L sea salt, 2 g/L yeast extract, 5-45 g/L glucose) Temperature: 25°C Light: dark conditions	nd	nd	45.17±0.71 (15-27 g/L glucose) 45.84±0.52 (80% medium replacement ratio)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

39.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
8-16% protein ²⁴⁰ 22-28% lipid 40-60% starch	nd	nd	22:6(n-3) DHA 36-41% ²⁴⁰ --- 22:6(n-3) DHA 20% ^e --- C12:0 3.08-3.88% ^f C14:0 12.82-14.28% C16:0 18.77-20.25% C18:0 2.19-3.43% C18:1 11.40-12.18% 22:6(n-3) 48.53-49.12%

39.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *C. cohnii* P10-012 (not distributed)
Location: Roscoff, France

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40. *Karlodinium veneficum*

A dinoflagellate common in coast environments that occasionally forms harmful blooms associated with fish kills due to the production of cytotoxic and ichthyotoxic compounds.

Commonly cultivated strains include:

CCMP 1974, CCMP 2936, CCMP 2064, ICMB 252, MD5, ICMB-256, ICMB-258, ICMB-259, ICMB-261, ICMB-266, ICMB-270, ICMB-271, ICMB-274, ICMB-275, ICMB-277, ICMB-282

40.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCMP 2936 ²⁴³	System: 300 mL T-flasks Medium: L1 basal culture medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 30±3 μmol.m ⁻² s ⁻¹ , 16 h L : 8 h D	nd	4.21·10 ⁴ cells/mL/d	nd
CCMP 2064 ²⁴⁴	System: nd Medium: ESAW H1 medium Carbon source: cryptophytes prey Temperature: 20°C Light: 100 μmol.m ⁻² s ⁻¹ , 12 h L : 12 h D	nd	nd	0.75·10 ⁶ cells/mL
ICMB 252 ²⁴⁵	System: 2 L Nalgene flasks Medium: L1 medium ²⁴⁶ Carbon source: cryptophytes prey Temperature: 21 ± 1°C Light: 110 μmol.m ⁻² s ⁻¹ , 12 h L : 12 h D		0.14 d ⁻¹	16.1 g/L (wet biomass)
CCMP 1974, CCMP 2064, MD5 ²⁴⁷	System: nd Medium: f/2 medium Temperature: 20°C Light: 75 μmol.m ⁻² day ⁻¹ , 12 h L : 12 h D	nd	nd	nd

ICMB-256, ICMB-258, ICMB-259, ICMB-261, ICMB-266, ICMB-270, ICMB-271, ICMB-274, ICMB-275, ICMB-277, ICMB-282 ²⁴⁸	System: 1.3 L Pyrex bottles Medium: L1 medium ²⁴⁶ Carbon source: <i>Rhodomonas salina</i> prey Temperature: 18°C Light: 120 $\mu\text{mol.m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$, 12 h L : 12 h D	nd	0.27-0.53 d ⁻¹	60960- 86600 cells/mL
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

40.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
nd	nd	nd	C12:0 0.6%, C14:1 0.6%, C14:0 6.5%, C15:1 1.2%, C15:0 0.5%, C16:0 11.3%, C17:1 8.5%, C17:0 0.9%, C18:3 1.9%, C18:2 0.2%, C18:1 1.0%, C18:0 19.3%, C20:5 0.4%, C20:4 1.3%, C20:3 4.4%, C20:1 0.8%, C20:0 0.3%, C21:0 2.2%, C22:0 0.5% ²⁴⁵ C14:0 2.0% (MD5), 17.0% (2064) C16:0 23.0% (MD5), 28.8% (2064) C16:1 2.8% (MD5), 2.9% (2064) C18:0 8.8% (MD5), 5.9% (2064) C18:1n9 17.2% (MD5), 10.6% (2064) C18:1 3.6% (MD5), 1.8% (2064) C18:2n6 3.5% (MD5), 3.3% (2064) C18:3n3 2.8% (MD5), 1.3% (2064) C18:4n3 3.9% (MD5), 3.2% (2064) C18:5n3 7.3% (MD5), 4.9% (2064) C22:5n3 0.3% (MD5), 0.3% (2064) C22:6n3 11.5% (MD5), 8.0% (2064) ²⁴⁷ C8:0 0-6.6%, C11:0 0-2.6%, C12:0 0-5.8%, C14:0 0-5.1%, C14:1 0-1.4%, C15:0 0-6.2%, C15:1 0-7.1%, C16:0 8.8-18.9%, C16:1 0-2.8%, C17:0 0-0.7%, C17:1 0-0.8%, C18:0 0-4.6%, C18:1 0-3.9%, C18:2 0-3.2%, C18:3 0-21.6%, C20:5 0-0.2%, C22:6 0-5.9%, C24:0 0-0.3%, C24:1 0-1.4%, Saturated fatty acid 16.6-29.3% Monounsaturated fatty acid 0-7.1% Polyunsaturated fatty acid 0-23.8% ²⁴⁸

40.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Bigelow NCMA](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *K. veneficum* CCMP426, CCMP2936
Location: East Boothbay Barcelona, US

- **Name:** [Institut de Ciències del Mar-CSIC](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Strain(s) available: *K. veneficum* ICMB-256, ICMB-258, ICMB-259, ICMB-261, ICMB-266, ICMB-270, ICMB-271, ICMB-274, ICMB-275, ICMB-277, ICMB-282
Location: Barcelona, Spain

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Rhodophyta (Red algae)

Red algae are a large and diverse group of algae, the majority of which are found on tropical and temperature marine shores, and the majority of which are macroscopic algae ¹⁴⁹. They lack flagella, and their plastids contain phycobilins, but lack chlorophyll *b* and *c*. Many red algal species are economically important, producing pigments and polyunsaturated fatty acids, as well as gelling polysaccharides such as agarose and carrageen ¹⁴⁹.

Major classes

No. of species in Algaebase

Cyanidiophyceae	6
Porphyridiophyceae	10
Rhodellophyceae	8
Bangiophyceae	183
Florideophyceae	7190

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above.

Class: Cyanidiophyceae

41. *Galdieria sulphuraria*

A unicellular red microalga which grows efficiently in extreme environments with acidic conditions and high temperatures. *G. sulphuraria* produces a large amount of biomass and many beneficial compounds ²⁴⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
074 W, 064/309

41.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
074 W ²⁴⁹	System: 300 mL shaking flasks Medium: modified 2 Allen's medium Carbon source: glucose (for mixotrophic and heterotrophic growth) Temperature: 42°C Light: 50 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ continuous light or none	nd	nd	3.8 \pm 0.2 (mixotrophic)
064/309 ²⁵⁰	System: 5 L glass cylindrical bioreactors Medium: Allen medium Carbon source: glycerol (for heterotrophic growth) Light: 150 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ (for phototrophic growth) L:D cycle nd	nd	nd	5.7 (autotrophic) 29 (heterotrophic)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

41.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
26–32% protein ²⁵⁰ 63–69% carbohydrate 11-18% lipid	nd	575 mg/kg astaxanthin ²⁵⁰ 387 mg/kg lutein 12 mg/kg chlorophyll-a 4.5-79 g/kg allophycocyanin 0.2-0.5 g/kg phycocyanin 3.3-6.5 g/kg phycoerytrin	C14:0 0.9-2.7% ²⁵⁰ C16:0 14.7-39.4% C16:1 2.4% C18:0 4.7% C18:1 8.6-57.5% C18:2 19.5-45.2% C18:3 1.1-2.7%

Class: Porphyridiophyceae

42. *Porphyridium purpureum*

A species of marine red algae belonging to the Porphyridiophyceae family. It presents high potential to produce B-phycoerythrin (B-PE), long chain polyunsaturated fatty acids (LC-PUFAs) and exopolysaccharides (EPS) which are excellent feedstock for food, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals ²⁵¹. *Porphyridium cruentum* (S.F.Gray) is considered to be a synonym of *Porphyridium purpureum* (Bory) ³³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
SCS-02, CCAP 1380/3, CoE1

42.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
SCS-02 ²⁵²	System: Glass column PBR Medium: ASW medium Temperature: 25±1°C Light: 350 µmol/m ² /s, continuous light	nd	nd	5.54 (high nitrogen)
CCAP 1380/3 ⁴³	System: two 600 L PBRs <i>(one for Batch Culture and another for semi-continuous culture)</i> Medium: f/2 commercial medium (<i>Cell-hi F2P, Varicon</i>) Temperature: those registered in Summer season in Wales (11-22°C) Light: those registered in Summer season in Wales (average of 376.4 µmol/m ² /s)	26.60 (Batch) 47.04 (Semi-continuous)	72.5 (Batch) 145 (Semi-continuous)	0.97 (Batch) 1.04 (Semi-continuous)

CoE1 ²⁵³	System: 1 L flasks Medium: ASW, KOCK, Pringsheim II and f/2 medium. Temperature: 25°C Light: from 110 to 220 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous light	nd	nd	9.95 (ASW medium) 9.25 (Pringsheim II medium) 8.34 (KOCK medium) 2.58 (f/2 medium)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

42.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
47.1% protein ²⁵² (high nitrogen) 12% lipid (high nitrogen) 52.1% carbohydrate (low nitrogen) --- ~ 15-22% protein ⁴³ ~ 17-20% lipid ~ 15-25% carbohydrate	nd	nd	C16:0 ~32% ²⁵² C16:1 ~2% C18:0 ~1% C18:1 ~2% C18:2 ~11% C20:4 ~27% C20:5 ~15% --- C16:0 13.32% ²⁵³ C18:0 2.32% C18:2 8.38% C20:3 1.26% C20:4 9.03% C20:5 2.60% Others 2.90% (220 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 3 L/min of aeration)

42.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. purpureum* AC120, AC121, AC122
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France

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- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *P. purpureum* CCAP 1380/11, 1380/1A, 1380/3, 1380/5, 1380/9
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Algal BioSciences – National University of Ireland](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: biotechnology, ecophysiology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Porphyridium purpureum*²⁵⁴, *Pavlova lutheri*²³⁰**Location:** Galway, Ireland
- Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology.
Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):
 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris*⁹¹, *Arthrospira maxima*⁹², *Nannochloropsis* spp.⁹³, *Micractinum inermum*¹⁴, *Porphyridium purpureum*^{42,43}, *Nostoc* sp., *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.**Location:** Swansea, UK
- Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Anabaena* sp.^{59,60}, *Porphyridium purpureum*⁶⁰, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*⁶⁰, *Nostoc*⁶⁰, *Dunaliella salina*⁶¹**Location:** Sevilla, Spain
- Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarchnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium*

*baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², ***Porphyridium purpureum*** (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, *Rhodella violacea*⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

- **Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on¹¹⁹:

- *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, ***Porphyridium cruentum***, *Synechocystis* sp., *T-isochrysis lutea*

Location: European Marine Science Park, Argyl, Scotland

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Class: Rhodellophyceae

43. *Rhodella* sp.

A Rhodellophyceae strain of red microalgae that produces unique bioactive substances including exopolysaccharides (EPS). Only phototrophic growth has been demonstrated for members of this genus ²⁵⁵.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1388/5, UTEX LB2320

43.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
<i>Rhodella violacea</i> CCAP 1388/5 ²⁵⁶	System: Flasks in growth chamber Medium: f/2-RSE Carbon source: air bubbling at 1.5 - 2 L/min Temperature: 8, 14, 20 and 26°C Light: 60 μmol/m ² /s, continuous	nd	nd	0.55 (8°C) 0.70 (14°C) 0.90 (20°C) (g _{AFDW} /L)
<i>Rhodella</i> sp. APOT_15 ²⁵⁷	System: 60 mL borosilicate test tubes Medium: f/2, 3xN f/2, 3xP f/2 Carbon source: nd Temperature: 15 °C Light: 50 μmol/m ² /s, continuous	nd	nd	Specific growth rate (μ/d) 0.3 (x3 N) 0.2 (x3 P) 0.1 (control)

<i>Rhodella reticulata</i> UTEX LB2320 ²⁵⁸	System: 200 mL vessels Medium: modified Brody Emerson nutrient medium Carbon source: 2% CO ₂ Temperature: 18-34°C Light: 260 μmol/m ² /s, constant illumination	nd	nd	1.65 (18°C) 2.70 (22°C) 4.20 (26°C) 4.50 (28°C) 1.45 (34°C) (g _{ADW} /L)
<i>Rhodella reticulata</i> UTEX LB2320 ²⁵⁸	System: 200 mL vessels Medium: modified Brody Emerson nutrient medium Carbon source: 2% CO ₂ Temperature: 18-34°C Light: 520 μmol/m ² /s, constant illumination	nd	nd	1.50 (18°C) 2.30 (22°C) 3.95 (26°C) 3.60 (28°C) 1.20 (34°C) (g _{ADW} /L)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

43.2 Biomass characteristics of *R. violacea*

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
nd	nd	Total pigments (mg/g) ²⁵⁶ 7.4 (8°C) 15.1 (14°C) 12.6 (20°C) 11.2 (26°C)	C14:0 1.45% ²⁵⁶ C14:1 0.37% C16:0 28.67% C16:1(n-7) 3.85% C18:0 1.08% C18:1(n-9) 1.27% C18:1(n-7) 6.24% C18:2(n-6) 1.06% C20:3(n-6) 0.99% C20:4(n-3) 2.60% C20:4(n-6) 14.33% C20:5(n-3) 33.62% (at 20°C after 14 days)

43.3 Biomass characteristics of *Rhodella* sp.

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
protein 26% ²⁵⁷ lipid 13% carbohydrate 49% (x3 N)		Chl α (mg/g) ²⁵⁷ 0.2 (x3 N) 0.6 (x3 P) 0.2 (control)	
protein 47% lipid 7% carbohydrate 42% (x3 P)	nd	Zeaxanthin (mg/g) 0.52 (x3 N) 0.43 (x3 P) 0.42 (control)	nd
protein 34% lipid 2% carbohydrate 56% (control)		Phycobiliprotein (% DW) 0.8 (x3 N) 0.96 (x3 P) 1.1 (control)	

43.4 Biomass characteristics of *R. reticulata*

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
(First value at 260, second at 520 μmol/m ² /s) ²⁵⁸ protein 36%, 42% lipid 9.4%, 11% carbohydrate 28%, 27% (18°C)			C16:0 29% ²⁵⁸ C16:1 16% C18:1 8% C18:2 3% C18:3 4% C20:4 0.1% C20:5 27% (18°C, 260 μmol/m ² /s)
protein 33%, 26% lipid 10.2%, 7.1% carbohydrate 31%, 37% (27°C)	nd	nd	C16:0 29% C16:1 18% C18:1 3% C18:2 2% C18:3 2% C20:4 6% C20:5 46% (27°C, 260 μmol/m ² /s)
protein 22%, 15% lipid 7%, 4.5% carbohydrate 38%, 43% (34°C)			

43.5 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *R. violacea* AC752, *R. maculata* AC753
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *R. violacea* CCAP1388/2, 1388/5, 1388/6
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- **Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *R. maculata* RCC655, 6690, *Rhodella* sp. RCC7795, 7796, 7797
Location: Roscoff, France
- **Name:** [LIENSs - Littoral, Environment and Societies](#), at University of La Rochelle
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Chemistry, environment, medical, nutraceuticals, pharmaceuticals. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Alexandrium minutum*⁶², *Alexandrium tamarense*⁶², *Bigelowiella natans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans*⁶², *Chaetoceros calcitrans* f. *pumillum*⁶², *Chaetoceros gracilis*⁶², *Chaetoceros minus*⁶², *Chaetoceros mulleri*⁶², *Chaetoceros* sp. *Tenuissimus* like⁶², *Chlorella autotrophica*⁶², *Chlorella vulgaris*⁶², *Chloroarachnion reptans*⁶², *Closterium baillyanum*⁶², *Cyanophora paradoxa*^{62,63}, *Cylindrotheca closterium*⁶⁴, *Dunaliella salina*^{62,65}, *Dunaliella* sp.⁶², *Dunaliella tertiolecta*^{62,66}, *Emiliana huxleyi*⁶², *Haematococcus pluvialis*⁶², *Heterocapsa triquetra*⁶⁷, *Isochrysis galbana*⁶², *Nitzschia* sp.⁶², *Odontella aurita*⁶², *Ostreococcus tauri*⁶², *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*⁶², *Porphyridium purpureum* (*Porphyridium cruentum*)^{65,68,69}, ***Rhodella violacea***⁶², *Rhodomonas salina*^{62,70}, *Scenedesmus acutus*⁶², *Scenedesmus obliquus*⁶², *Skeletonema grethae*⁶², *Tetraselmis suecica*⁶², *Thalassiosira pseudonana*⁶², *Tisochrysis lutea*⁷¹, *Euglena proxima*⁶²

The research team at LIENSs works in close collaboration with the [Laboratory of phycotoxines \(IFREMER\)](#) at Nantes, France.

In addition to the microalgae above, the team at LIENSs have experience with the model species *Spirulina* (*A. platensis*), from which they develop extraction process.

Locations: La Rochelle, France

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Cyanobacteria (Blue-green algae)

The cyanobacteria are a large group of photoautotrophic Gram-negative bacteria. They are perhaps the earliest microorganisms to exhibit oxygenic photosynthesis, around 2.45 billion years ago¹⁴⁹. They are morphologically diverse, occurring in various unicellular, colony forming and filamentous forms. They are also metabolically diverse, contributing to global carbon, nitrogen, sulphur and other biogeochemical cycles, and can be found in most aquatic and terrestrial habitats¹⁴⁹.

Major classes

Cyanophyceae

No. of species in Algaebase

5462

Values were obtained from Algaebase. The classes highlighted in bold contain strains represented in this catalogue. These strains are denoted in the phylogenetic tree above.

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Class: Cyanophyceae

44. *Anabaena cylindrica*

A freshwater filamentous cyanobacteria with robust growth characteristics and a source of pigments. It has nitrogen-fixation characteristics and some strains have been observed to produce hydrogen ²⁵⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1403/2A, IAM M1 (PCC 7122), 10 C (CSMA)

44.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1403/2A ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: BG11 Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 μmol/m ² /s, 16 h L: 8 h D	0.078	0.171	2.4
IAM M1 (PCC 7122) ²⁶⁰	System: 5 PBR's in series (0.2 dm ³ each) Medium: Detmer medium Carbon source: CO ₂ 6% Temperature: 298 K (24.85°C) Light: 1 klx, L:D cycle N/A	nd	nd	From: 0.667 (1 st PBR) to: ~2.66 (5 th PBR)
10 C ²⁶¹ (CSMA)	System: Fermentor (1 L) Medium: BG11 Carbon source: CO ₂ and acetate Temperature: 25°C Light: 32 W cool white fluorescent lamp. Continuous illumination	nd	nd	~0.3 (BG11) ~0.6 (BG11+acetate)

PCC 7937 ⁶⁰	System: PBR (2 L) Medium: BG11 Temperature: 30°C Light: 3000 μmol/m ² /s, 12 h L: 12 h D	0.38 ± 0.14	nd	nd
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

44.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
56% protein ³⁸ 7% lipid 25% carbohydrate --- 38.09±1.18 % protein ⁶⁰ 16.03±0.90 % lipid 37.07±2.26 % carbohydrate --- 43-56% protein ⁵³ 4-7% lipid 25-30% carbohydrate	nd	nd	nd

44.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. cylindrica* AC163
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. cylindrica* CCAP 1403/2A, 1403/2B, 1403/30
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection \(LEGE\) at CIIMAR](#)
CIIMAR is an EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Anabena cf. cylindrica* LEGE 00235

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Read more about the services offered by the LEGE culture collection in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).

Location: Porto, Portugal

- **Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. cylindrica* BEA 0794B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain

- **Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation type: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Anabaena sp.*^{59,60}, *Porphyridium purpureum*⁶⁰**Location:** Sevilla, Spain

- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.
Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Nannochloropsis, Dunaliella, Nostoc, Anabaena***Location:** Almería, Spain

45. *Arthrospira platensis*

A filamentous cylindrical cyanobacteria that is commonly known commercially as spirulina. It is widely cultivated as a food source and nutritional supplement particularly because it is rich in protein and contains essential amino acids ²⁶². It is commonly cultivated in open ponds but can also be grown in photobioreactors. It can grow under a range of temperature conditions but has optimum growth at higher temperatures, ~35°C ²⁶³.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
SAG 21.99, SAG 85.79, SAG 257.80, WH879

45.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
SAG 85.79 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: Zarrouk medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, 16h L: 8h D	0.06	0.21	3.1
SAG 21.99 ²⁶⁴	System: PBR (0.5 L) Medium: Zarrouk medium Temperature: 30°C Light: 120 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous light	nd	0.231	2.274
Mixed culture: <i>Arthrospira</i> sp. ²⁶⁵	System: outdoor raceway ponds, surface area 100 m ² , culture depth 30 cm Medium: SOT medium Temperature: outdoors Light: outdoors	nd	34 (g/m ² /d, accounts for irradiance surface area)	0.62
WH879 ²⁶⁶	System: Fed-batch PBR (1 L) Medium: Zarrouk medium Temperature: 28°C Light: 300 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, Continuous light	nd	0.594 (feeding only Nitrate)	6.78 (feeding fresh medium)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

45.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
62% protein ³⁸ 9% lipid 20% carbohydrate	nd	90 mg/g phycocyanin ³⁸ 39.8 mg/g chlorophyll 3.8 mg/g carotene - - - 0.28-1.5% chlorophyll ²⁶⁴ - - - 5-12% phycocyanin ²⁶⁵ - - - 16.1±0.2% phycocyanin ²⁶⁶	C16:0 40.1% ³⁸ C16:1 9.2% C18:0 1.2% C18:1 5.4% C18:2 17.9% C18:3 18.3% other 7.9%

45.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. platensis* CH-9
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *A. platensis* BEA 0007B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricorutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea***Locations:** Lisbon, Portugal
- Name:** [Algalimento](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated partner

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Algalimento currently produces all-year round high-quality biomass of ²⁶⁷:

- *Tetraselmis sp., Spirulina canariensis, Dunaliella salina*

Locations: Lisbon, Portugal

- **Name:** [AlgoSource](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing

Expertise: engineering, large-scale development, industrial ecology. Know-how on *Spirulina* and its principal ingredient phycocyanin. The company is also working on extracting molecules of interest from other microalgae ²⁶⁸:

- *Spirulina, Chlorella, Scenedesmus, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis*

Locations: Saint-Nazaire, France

- **Name:** [Aqualgae](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: design and installation of high-productivity photobioreactors, suppliers of culturing media, inoculums, and lyophilised cultures of ⁸⁶:

- *Chlorella, Haematococcus, Arthrospira, Tetraselmis, Isochrysis, Pavlova, Chaetoceros, Skeletonema, Nitzschia, Rhodomonas, Nannochloropsis*

Locations: Diana do Castelo, Portugal; and A Coruña, Spain

- **Name:** [Bretagne Sipurline](#)

Business/organisation type: producer

Expertise: nutraceuticals. The company sells *Spirulina* in various pack sizes.

Locations: Landévant, France

- **Name:** [International Iberian Nanotechnology Laboratory \(INL\)](#)

EnhanceMicroAlgae partner

Business/organisation type: research and development

Expertise: nanotechnology, nanoscience, encapsulation, food processing and nutrition, nutraceuticals, safety assessment, biotechnology, engineering. Research outputs include (but not limited to):

- *Arthrospira platensis* ²⁶⁹

Locations: Braga, Portugal

- **Name:** [La Voie Bleue](#)

Business/organisation type: association

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Expertise: marketing and valorisation, nutraceuticals, sustainable food chains. Promotes Spirulina (and other microalgae) for food by local production, and supports other projects. Read about La Voie Bleue’s services in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#)
Locations: Toulouse, France

- **Name:** [NeoAlgae](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: aquaculture, cosmetics, nutraceuticals, biotechnology. The company produces a wide range of Spirulina-based products for food, cosmetics, and agriculture ²⁷⁰. Their R&D division specialises on various extracts from *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Isochrysis galbana*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana* ²⁷¹
Locations: Asturias, Spain

- **Name:** [OMA – Olivier MicroAlgues](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, downstream processing
Expertise: nutraceuticals. The company sells *Spirulina* in various packs and formats.
Location: Haute-Goulaine, France

- **Name:** [Spanish Society of Microalgae and Subproducts](#) (SEMS)

Business/organisation type: producer, research and development
Expertise: biotechnology, chemistry, marketing and valorisation. The company offers various laboratory services and products for agriculture, with various microalgae being produced on a continuous basis ²⁷²:
- *Arthrospira platensis*, *Nannochloropsis gaditana*, *Scenedesmus* sp., and *Scenedesmus subspicatus*

Locations: Rota, Spain

- **Name:** [Scottish Bioenergy Ltd.](#)

Business/organisation type: producer, technology manufacturer, downstream processing
Expertise: energy, environment, biotechnology. Company products include a Spirulina-based colourant (ScotBio Blue) and protein (ScotBio protein), as well as fresh/dry Spirulina.
Locations: Newhouse, Scotland

- **Name:** [Technature](#)

Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: cosmetics. The company offers a wide line of cosmetic products, some of which are derived from Spirulina extracts (e.g. Toning lotion, Radiance boost marine serum, algae heating body wrap) ²⁷³
Locations: Dirinon, France

- **Name:** [Tinctura](#)
Business/organisation type: producer, downstream processing
Expertise: nutraceuticals, large-scale development. Tinctura develops and produces aqueous extracts rich in phycocyanin from French Spirulina.
Locations: Ploudaniel, France
- **Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.
Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - **Spirulina**, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, *Nostoc*, *Anabaena***Location:** Almería, Spain
- **Name:** [Varicon Aqua](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: SME
Expertise: Providing resources to the algae and aquaculture sector. Their work involving microalgae includes:
 - **Spirulina**, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Nannochloropsis sp.*, *Tetraselmis suecica*, *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*.**Location:** Worcester, United Kingdom

46. *Lyngbya lutea*

Formerly known as *Oscillatoria lutea* (C.Agardh)³³. A cyanobacteria strain that has interest as a source of chemicals including butylated hydroxytoluene, which has antioxidant characteristics²⁷⁴.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1459/3

46.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1459/3 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.04	0.05	0.76
nd ²⁷⁵ (<i>Oscillatoria lutea</i> var. <i>contorta</i>) obtained from the collection of the University of Texas	System: 500 mL flasks (250 mL working volume) Medium: grown on barley straw extract Temperature: 20°C Light: 65 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	~600 ug L (measured as <i>Chlorophyll a</i>)

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

46.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigments	Fatty acids
48% protein ³⁸ 9% lipid 18% carbohydrate	nd	9.8 mg/g chlorophyll ³⁸ 1.7 mg/g carotenoids	nd

46.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- **Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Lyngbya* sp. CCAP 1446/10, 1446/7, 1473/2, 1473/4, *Oscillatoria lutea* var. *contorta* CCAP 1459/3, *Oscillatoria* sp. CCAP 1459/13
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

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47. *Microcystis aeruginosa*

A cyanobacteria strain known for toxic bloom formation. It can produce neurotoxins and is also a source of butylated hydroxytoluene, which has antioxidant characteristics ²⁷⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1450/1, FACHB-469.

47.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1450/1 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.04	0.06	0.68
FACHB-469 ²⁷⁷	System: 250 mL flasks (150 mL working volume) Medium: BG11 medium with dissolved organic carbon, DOM Temperature: 25°C Light: 50 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	1.7x10 ⁷ cells/mL

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

47.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
66% protein ³⁸ 9% lipid 8% carbohydrate --- ~4.5-8 pg cell ⁻¹ protein ²⁷⁷ ~2-12 pg cell ⁻¹ polysaccharides (under various organic sources)	nd	~0.4-0.55 ug 10 ⁶ cell ⁻¹ chlorophyll content ²⁷⁸	nd

47.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Laboratoire Phycotoxines IFREMER](#)
Business/organisation: research and development, environmental monitoring
Expertise: chemistry, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):
 - *Tisochrysis lutea* ²²¹, *Microcystis aeruginosa* ²²²

The research team at IFREMER works in close collaboration with the EnhanceMicroAlgae team at [LIENSs, University of La Rochelle](#), France.

Location: Nantes, France

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48. *Nostoc* sp.

A cyanobacteria strain that is grown as a food and feed source, and a nutritional supplement in Asia due to its protein and vitamin constituents ²⁷⁹.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
CCAP 1403/17, TISTR 8872, TISTR 8873

48.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
CCAP 1403/17 ³⁸	System: PBR Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 22°C Light: 70 μmol/m ² /s, 16h L: 8h D	0.122	0.197	1.38
TISTR 8872 ²⁸⁰	System: Conical flasks (300 mL working volume) Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 28±1°C Light: 60 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	0.3±0.0
TISTR 8873 ²⁸⁰	System: Conical flasks (300 mL working volume) Medium: BG11 medium Temperature: 28±1°C Light: 60 μmol/m ² /s, 12h L: 12h D	nd	nd	0.2±0.04

^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

48.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
42% protein ³⁸ 8% lipid 33% carbohydrate --- From 30.66±0.58 to 32.85±1.52% starch ²⁸⁰	nd	0.6 mg/g chlorophyll ³⁸ 1.7 mg/g carotenoids	nd

48.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [Algobank-Caen](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc commune* AC661
Location: Université de Caen Normandie, Caen, France
- Name:** [Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection \(LEGE\) at CIIMAR](#)
CIIMAR is an EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. LEGE 06158, 06077, 07365, 13413, 12447, 12448, 12449, 12450, 12451, 12453, 12454, 12456,
 Read more about the services offered by the LEGE culture collection in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Porto, Portugal
- Name:** [Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa CCAP](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. CCAP 1403/17, 1453/25, 1453/27, 1453/28, 1453/31, 1453/4
Location: Scottish Marine institute, Scotland, UK
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. A12.448
Location: Roscoff, France

- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Nostoc* sp. BEA 1063B, 1249B, 1559B, 0874B, 1279B, 1605B , 0886B, 1557B, 0877B, 1039B, 1454B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [Algal Research Group, Swansea University](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: Higher education, research & development.
Expertise: Microalgae biotechnology, biomass characterization, upstream and downstream process, chemistry, ecophysiology, engineering, large-scale development, molecular biology. Research expertise with microalgae includes (but is not limited to):

 - *Scenedesmus obliquus* and *Chlorella vulgaris* ⁹¹, *Arthrospira maxima* ⁹², *Nannochloropsis* spp. ⁹³, *Micractinum inermum* ¹⁴, *Porphyridium purpureum* ^{42,43}, ***Nostoc* sp.**, *Isochrysis galbana* and over 25 common microalgae species including green algae, diatoms, cyanobacteria and dinoflagellates.

Location: Swansea, UK
- Name:** [IBVF - Instituto de Bioquímica Vegetal y Fotosíntesis, Microalgae Biotechnology Group](#)
Business/organisation: research & development
Expertise: bioenergy, ecophysiology, molecular biology. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Anabaena* sp. ^{59,60}, *Porphyridium purpureum* ⁶⁰, *Scenedesmus vacuolatus* ⁶⁰, ***Nostoc*** ⁶⁰, *Dunaliella salina* ⁶¹

Location: Sevilla, Spain
- Name:** [Universidad de Almería](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae Associated Partner
Business/organisation type: University, non profit organisation.
Expertise: Scale up of microalgae-related processes. Research outputs involving microalgae include (but are not limited to):

 - *Spirulina*, *Chlorella*, *Scenedesmus*, *Nannochloropsis*, *Dunaliella*, ***Nostoc***, *Anabaena*

Location: Almería, Spain

49. Synechococcus sp.

A genus of cyanobacteria found in aquatic environments worldwide that contributes to global primary productivity. Originally thought to be obligate phototrophs, some strains have also been reported to grow mixotrophically ²⁸¹. Various strains of this genus serve as model organisms for basic photosynthesis research, as well as commonly being employed for genetic engineering studies ²⁸².

Commonly cultivated strains include:
PCC 7002, PCC 7942, UTEX 2973 ²⁸²

49.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
nd ²⁸³ <i>isolated from Gua Tempurung, a cave in Malaysia</i>	System: 250 mL flasks Medium: BG11 Carbon source: nd Temperature: 25°C Light: 25 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ in 12:12h L:D	nd	nd	5.56 <i>(exponential)</i> 3.85 <i>(late stationary)</i>
PCC 11901 PCC 7002 PCC 7942 UTEX 2973 ²⁸²	System: Erlenmeyer flasks (25 mL culture volume) Medium: AD7 or BG11 Carbon source: 1% CO ₂ Temperature: 30°C Light: 150-750 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$, continuous illumination	nd	nd	18.3 9.3 6.3 6.5
MK568070 ²⁸⁴	System: 2.8L PBR Medium: artificial seawater + wastewater Carbon source: 3% CO ₂ Temperature: 25°C Light: 80 $\mu\text{mol}/\text{m}^2/\text{s}$ in 12:12h L:D	nd	nd	0.767

PCC 7002 ²⁸⁵	System: 110L flat panel PBR and 1025L ponds (25 cm culture depth) Medium: /A+ medium Carbon source: 2% CO ₂ Temperature: 30°C or ambient Light: 150 μmol/m ² /s continuous illumination, or sunlight	nd	0.35 g/L/day 9.2 g/m ² /day <i>(flat-panel PBR)</i> 0.036 g/L/day 8.8 g/m ² /day <i>(outdoor pond)</i>	1.5 <i>(flat-panel PBR)</i> 0.35 <i>(outdoor pond)</i>
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

49.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
protein 55% carbohydrate 6% lipid 43% <i>(exponential phase)</i>	nd	chlorophyll α 0.13 mg/L carotenoids 0.065 mg/L <i>(exponential phase)</i> chlorophyll α 0.10 mg/L carotenoids 0.040 mg/L <i>(late stationary phase)</i> ²⁸³	C14:0 13.2% C15:0 1.2% C16:0 43.0% C16:1c 21.2% C16:1t 1.75% C17:0 2.5% C18:0 8.8% C18:1c 5.9% C18:1t 2.15% ²⁸⁴
protein 57% carbohydrate 6% lipid 68% <i>(early stationary phase)</i> ²⁸³			

protein 15.1% carbohydrate 18.9% lipid 21.4% ²⁸⁴			
protein ~55% carbohydrate ~5% lipid ~5% ²⁸⁵			

49.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechococcus* sp. CCAP 1400/1, 1450/7, 1479/10, 1479/11, 1479/13, 1479/14, 1479/22, 1479/5, 1479/9, *S. leopoliensis* CCAP 1405/1, *S. elongatus* CCAP 1479/1A, 1479/1B,
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom

- Name:** [Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection \(LEGE\) at CIIMAR](#)
CIIMAR is an EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechococcus* sp. LEGE 11471, 11466, 11379, 11381, 11394, 11428, 06324, 06306, 07172, 11428, *S. nidulans* LEGE 06156, 06322, 07171
Read more about the services offered by the LEGE culture collection in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Porto, Portugal
- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechococcus* sp. RCC29, 30, 31, plus an additional 450 strains numbered between RCC32 and 7260
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechococcus* sp. BEA 0851B, 1024B, 1139B, 1031B, 1561B, 1567B, 1579B, 1514B, *S. elongatus* BEA 0058, 0059B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., ***Synechococcus* sp.**, *Synechocystis* sp., *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea***Locations:** Lisbon, Portugal
- Name:** [ABIMS – Analysis and Bioinformatics for Marine Science](#)
Business/organisation: platform, informatics
Expertise: bioinformatics, database, metagenomics, molecular biology, software development, transcriptomics. Research outputs associated to the company, as listed in their publications page, include (but are not limited to):
 - *Phaeodactylum tricornutum* ¹⁸⁴, ***Synechococcus* sp.** ¹⁸⁵**Location:** Roscoff, France

50. Synechocystis sp.

A unicellular cyanobacteria with robust growth characteristics that has been posed as a promising strain for biodiesel production. An ideal genus for metabolic engineering, it is naturally transformable and was the first cyanobacteria to have its genome sequenced ²⁸⁶.

Commonly cultivated strains include:
PCC 6803, ATCC 27184

50.1 Cultivation characteristics

Strain	Cultivation Conditions	Mean biomass productivity ^a	Maximum productivity ^a	Maximum production ^a
GT-L	System: flat panel PBR Medium: BG11 Carbon source: 5000 ppm CO ₂ Temperature: 32°C Light: 220 μmol/m ² /s red light + 25 μmol/m ² /s blue light	nd	nd	0.125
GT-B				0.102
PCC 6803 ²⁸⁷				0.115
PCC 6803 ²⁸⁸	System: 1L PBR (0.06m diameter, 0.39m height) Medium: BG11 Carbon source: 0.5% CO ₂ Temperature: 34°C Light: 100-450 μmol/m ² /s, continuous illumination	nd	nd	0.775 (100 μmol/m ² /s) 1.469 (450 μmol/m ² /s)
nd ²⁸⁶ <i>obtained from Touchstone Research Laboratory, Triadelphia, WV, USA</i>	System: 2L glass bottles Medium: ASW/ADE media Carbon source: air 175 mL/min Temperature: 25°C Light: 200 μmol/m ² /s, continuous illumination	nd	0.151 <i>(batch)</i> 0.186 – 0.212 <i>(semicontinuous)</i>	nd

PCC 6803 ²⁸⁹	System: 1L column PBR Medium: BG11 Carbon source: 2% CO ₂ Temperature: 34°C Light: 45-450 μmol/m ² /s continuous illumination	nd	0.25 (batch)	2.53 (batch) 1.44 (semi-continuous)
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^a Unless otherwise specified, productivity is given in g/L/d and production in g/L

50.2 Biomass characteristics

Biomass composition	Element composition	Pigment composition	Fatty acid profile
protein 38% carbohydrate 34% (GT-L)	nd	chlorophyll α 1.2% carotenoids 0.40% phycocyanin 10.7% allophycocyanin 1.9% (PCC 6803) ²⁸⁷	C14:0 2% C14:1 0.5% C16:0 60% C16:1 4% C18:0 3% C18:1 7% C18:2 20% C18:3 3% ²⁸⁶
protein 56% carbohydrate 19% (GT-B)		chlorophyll 10.16 mg/g (batch)	
protein 55% carbohydrate 23% (PCC 6803) ²⁸⁷		10.68 mg/g (semi-continuous) ²⁸⁹	
lipid content 13.2% productivity 0.020 g/L/d (batch) 0.025-0.028 g/L/d (semi-continuous) ²⁸⁶			

50.3 Stakeholders in the Atlantic Area

- Name:** [CCAP Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechocystis* sp. CCAP 1480/4, *S. limnetica* CCAP 1480/5, *S. bourrellyi* CCAP1480/1
Location: Scottish Marine Institute, United Kingdom
- Name:** [Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection \(LEGE\) at CIIMAR](#)
CIIMAR is an EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechocystis* sp. LEGE 07211, 07367, 06025, 06017, 06083, 07073, 06079, 06005, *S. salina* LEGE 00040, 00038, 00030, 00032, 00037, 00036, 00031, 00029, 00028, 00027, 00041, 06155, 06099
Read more about the services offered by the LEGE culture collection in the [EnhanceMicroAlgae marketplace](#).
Location: Porto, Portugal

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- Name:** [Roscoff Culture Collection](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechocystis* sp. RCC1773
Location: Roscoff, France
- Name:** [Spanish Algae Bank](#)
Business/organisation type: bio-bank
Strain(s) available: *Synechocystis* sp. BEA 0839B, 0848B, 0771B, 0785B, 0849B, 1012B, 1138B, 0943B, 1427B, 1551B, 1555B, 1578B, 1829B, 1833B, 1844B, *S. salina* BEA 0840B, 1011B, 1574B
Location: Telde Gran Canaria, Spain
- Name:** [A4F – Algae 4 Future](#)
EnhanceMicroAlgae partner
Business/organisation type: bio-bank, producer, research and development, downstream processing
Expertise: biotechnology, engineering, large-scale development. Their microalgae track-production (large and pilot scale) includes ¹¹:
 - *Arthrospira platensis*, *Chlamydomonas* sp., *Chlorella vulgaris*, *Dunaliella salina*, *Haematococcus pluvialis*, *Lobosphaera incisa*, *Nannochloropsis oceanica*, *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Prorocentrum cassubicum*, *Raphidonema* sp., *Scenedesmus* sp., *Scotiellopsis* sp., *Synechococcus* sp., ***Synechocystis* sp.**, *Tetraselmis* sp., *Thalassiosira weissflogii*, *Tisochrysis lutea***Locations:** Lisbon, Portugal
- Name:** [Xanthella Ltd.](#)
Business/organisation type: research and development
Expertise: Design and test bespoke PBRs, consultancy, repair and recycling of old systems, active research and development. The company has worked on ¹¹⁹:
 - *Chaetoceros muelleri*, *Chlamydomonas acidophila*, *Chlorella sorokiniana*, *Dunaliella primolecta*, *Desmodesmus subspicatus*, *Fragilaria* sp., *Isochrysis galbana*, *Limnorphis robusta*, *Nannochloropsis* sp., *Phaeodactylum tricornutum*, *Porphyridium cruentum*, ***Synechocystis* sp.**, *T-isochrysis lutea***Location:** European Marine Science Park, Argyll, Scotland

Appendix 1. Media recipes

A compilation of the microalgae media recipes shown in this strain catalogue is presented in this appendix. The reader should be aware that recipes shown here follow the standard protocol where culturing medium is prepared by mixing specific quantities of stock solutions so as to reach the desired components' medium concentrations.

Unless otherwise specified, all media is prepared by carrying out the following protocol:

1. Prepare all necessary *stock solutions** by dissolving each component in 1 L of distilled H₂O (dH₂O);
2. Add/mix the corresponding quantity of stock solutions into dH₂O;
3. Bring final volume to 1 L;
4. Adjust pH if required; and
5. Autoclave (sterilize at 15 psi for 15 min).

* Preparation of *stock solutions* is very useful during media preparation as it reduces weighing errors, particularly for those components that are necessary in very small quantities (micronutrients). Whilst we have aimed to provide preparation instructions for stock solutions within all the media recipes presented here, the reader should be aware that stock solution's recipes can be modified accordingly so long as the final medium concentration of each component is met.

It is also important to note that microalgae media recipes have been subject to modifications (e.g. replacing one component for another, increasing or decreasing component concentrations, etc.) to fit the desired cultivation needs, such as optimisation of biomass or metabolite concentration, maximise nutrient uptake, etc. We would therefore encourage the reader to browse the open literature, where different variations of the recipes shown here, as well as many others, have been widely explored.

Useful sources for algal media recipes

- CCAP media recipes ²⁹⁰
- Algal Culturing Techniques, by Rober A. Andersen, Elsevier Academic Press (2005) ²⁹¹

A.1. Artificial Seawater (ASW) medium

ASW components and concentrations ²⁹⁰

Component	Stock solution g per 1000 mL H ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
<i>Extra salts</i>		3.75 mL
NaNO ₃	30	
Na ₂ HPO ₄	1.2	
K ₂ HPO ₄	1	
<i>Vitamin solution</i>		2.5 mL
Biotin	0.0002	
Calcium pantothenate	0.02	
Cyanocobalamin	0.004	
Folic acid	0.0004	
Inositol	1.0	
Nicotinic acid	0.02	
Thiamine HCl	0.1	
Thymine	0.6	
<i>Soil extract (SE1)</i>	See below	25 mL
Tricine		0.5 g

Soil extract (SE1)

Soil should be air-dried. Dried soil is autoclaved together with a volume of distilled water equivalent to double the volume of soil. Once autoclaved, the supernatant is decanted, filtered (Whatman No 1 paper), and placed in appropriate vessels until used for media preparation. Soil selection is an important consideration for ASW media. Readers are referred to the recipe provided by CCAP ²⁹⁰.

A.2. Blue-Green medium (BG11)

Mix stock solutions and bring to 1 L; adjust pH to 7.1 (with NaOH or HCl).

BG11 medium components and concentrations²⁹⁰

Component	Stock solution g per 500 mL dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaNO ₃	75	10 mL
K ₂ HPO ₄	2	10 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	3.75	10 mL
CaCl ₂ ·2 H ₂ O	1.80	10 mL
Citric acid	0.3	10 mL
Ammonium ferric citrate green	0.3	10 mL
EDTA·Na ₂	0.05	10 mL
Na ₂ CO ₃	1	10 mL
Trace metals solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL

Trace metals solution (also known as A5 + Co Trace metals solution)²⁹⁰

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
H ₃ BO ₃	2.860 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.810 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.220 g
CuSO ₂ ·5H ₂ O	0.08 g
Na ₂ MoO ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.39 g
Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.05 g

A.3. Bold's Basal Medium (BBM) and 3N-BBM

The recipe for BBM is presented below. 3N-BBM is identical to BBM medium but requiring 3 times the nitrogen (i.e. 3N) used in BBM.

BBM medium components and concentration ²⁹⁰

Component	Stock solution g per 400 mL dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
<i>Macronutrients</i>		
NaNO ₃	10	10 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	3	10 mL
NaCl	1	10 mL
K ₂ HPO ₄	3	10 mL
KH ₂ PO ₄	7	10 mL
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1	10 mL
<i>BBM trace elements solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL
<i>Boric acid solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL
<i>Alkaline EDTA solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL
<i>Acidified Iron solution</i>	See recipe below	1 mL

BBM trace elements solution ²⁹⁰

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	8.82 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.44 g
MoO ₃	0.71 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	1.57 g
Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.49 g

BBM additional solutions ²⁹⁰

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
<i>Boric acid solution</i>	
H ₃ BO ₃	11.42 g
<i>Alkaline EDTA solution</i>	
EDTA	50 g
KOH	31 g
<i>Acidified Iron solution</i>	
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	4.98 g
H ₂ SO ₄	1 mL

A.4. Chu 13 medium (Modified)

Chu 13 medium components and concentrations ²⁹²

Component	Quantity for 1L medium
KNO ₃	400 mg
K ₂ HPO ₄	80 mg
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	200 mg
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	107 mg
Fe citrate	20 mg
Citric acid	100 mg
<i>Micronutrients</i>	
CoCl ₂	0.02 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	5.72 mg
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	3.62 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.44 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.16 mg
Na ₂ MoO ₄	0.084 mg
H ₂ SO ₄ 0.072 N	1 drop

A.5. Conway medium

Conway medium components and concentrations ²⁹³

Component	Quantity for 1L medium
KNO ₃	100 mg
Na ₃ HPO ₄	20 mg
<i>Trace metals</i>	
Na ₂ H ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	45 mg
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	1.3 mg
ZnCl ₂	4.2 mg
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.36 mg
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	4 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	4 mg
(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	1.8 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	33.4 mg
<i>Vitamins</i>	
Thiamin HCl	0.2 mg
Cyanocobalamin	0.01 mg

A.6. Detmer medium (DM) modified

Detmer medium components and concentrations ²⁹⁴

Component	Quantity for 1 L medium
Ca (NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1 g
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.26 g
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.55 g
KCl	0.25 g
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.02 g
EDTA·2Na	0.2 g
<i>Trace elements</i>	
H ₃ BO ₃	0.0029 g
ZnCl ₂	0.00011 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.00181 g
(NH ₄) ₆ MoO ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.000018 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.00008 g

A.7. f/2 medium

This is a seawater medium, prepared by bringing up the final volume to 1 L with filtered natural seawater. Adjust pH to 8 with 1 M NaOH or HCl.

f/2 medium components and concentrations ²⁹⁰

Component	Stock solution qty per 1 L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaNO ₃	75 g	1 mL
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	5.65 g	1 mL
Trace metals solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
Vitamins solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL

f/2 trace metals solution ²⁹⁰

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Na ₂ EDTA	4.16 g
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	3.15 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.01 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.022 g
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.01 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.18 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.006 g

Vitamins solution ²⁹⁵ (filter-sterilise and store frozen).

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B ₁₂)	0.0005 g
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B ₁)	0.1 g
Biotin	0.0005 g

A.8. f/2+Si (Guillard's medium for diatoms)

This is a seawater medium, prepared by bringing up the final volume to 1 L with filtered natural seawater. Adjust pH to 8 with 1 M NaOH or HCl.

f/2 + Si medium components and concentrations ²⁹⁰

Component	Stock solution g per 1 L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaNO ₃	75	1 mL
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	5.65	1 mL
Trace metals solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
Vitamins solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
<i>Sodium metasilicate solution</i>		1 mL
Na ₂ SiO ₃ ·9H ₂ O	30 g	

F/2 + Si trace metals solution ²⁹⁰

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Na ₂ EDTA	4.16 g
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	3.15 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.01 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.022 g
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.01 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.18 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.006 g

Vitamins solution ²⁹⁰ (filter-sterilise and store frozen).

Component	Quantity per 1L dH ₂ O
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B ₁₂)	0.0005 g
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B ₁)	0.1 g
Biotin	0.0005 g

A.9. Jaworski's Medium (JM)

JM medium components and concentrations ²⁹⁰

Component	Stock solution g per 200 mL dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
Ca(NO ₃) ₂ ·4H ₂ O	4 g	1 mL
KH ₂ PO ₄	2.48 g	1 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	10 g	1 mL
NaHCO ₃	3.18 g	1 mL
<i>EDTA solution</i>		1 mL
EDTA·Fe·Na	0.45 g	
EDTA·Na ₂	0.45 g	
<i>Trace elements solution</i>		1 mL
H ₃ BO ₃	0.496 g	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.278 g	
(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.2 g	
Vitamins solution	<i>See recipe below</i>	1 mL
NaNO ₃	16 g	1 mL
Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·12H ₂ O	7.2 g	1 mL

Vitamins solution ²⁹⁰ (filter-sterilise and store frozen).

Component	Quantity per 200 mL dH ₂ O
Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B ₁₂)	0.0008 g
Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B ₁)	0.0008 g
Biotin	0.0008 g

A.10. Kuhl medium

Kuhl medium components and concentrations ¹¹⁴

Component	Quantity for 1 L medium
KNO ₃	1 g
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	0.621 g
Na ₂ HPO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	89 mg
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	246.5 mg
EDTA	9.3 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	0.061 mg
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	14.7 mg
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	6.95 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.287 mg
(NH ₄) ₆ Mo ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.01235 mg
MnSO ₄ ·H ₂ O	0.169 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.00249 mg

A.11. SOT medium

Bring final volume to 1 L and adjust pH to 9.

SOT medium components and concentrations ²⁹⁶

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
NaHCO ₃		16.8 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		0.5 g
NaNO ₃		2.5 g
K ₂ SO ₄		1 g
NaCl		1 g
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.2 g
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O		0.04 g
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.01 g
EDTA		0.08 g
<i>Trace metal Mix A5</i>		1 mL
H ₃ BO ₃	2.86	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.81	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.222	
NaMoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.39	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.079	
Co(NO ₃) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	49.4 mg	
<i>Trace metal Mix B6 (modified)</i>		1 mL
NH ₄ NO ₃	0.23	
K ₂ Cr(SO ₄) ₄ ·24H ₂ O	96 mg	
NiSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	47.8 mg	
Na ₂ WO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	17.9 mg	
Ti ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	40 mg	

A.12. Sueoka medium

Sueoka medium components and concentrations ¹¹³

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1L medium
KH ₂ PO ₄		0.72 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		1.44
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.02
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O		0.01
NH ₄ Cl		0.5
<i>Trace elements</i>		1 mL
<i>EDTA</i>	10	
H ₃ BO ₃	2.28	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	4.4	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.02	
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1	
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.32	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.32	
Mo ₇ O ₂₄ (NH ₄) ₆ ·4H ₂ O	0.22	

A.13. Walne's medium

Walne's medium components and concentrations ²¹⁵

Component	Stock solution g per 1 L dH ₂ O	Quantity used for 1 L medium
NaNO ₃	100	1 mL
EDTA (Disodium salt)	45	
H ₃ BO ₃	33.6	
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	20	
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	1.3	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.36	
<i>Trace metals solution</i>	<i>g per 100 mL</i>	1 mL
ZnCl ₂	2.1	
CoCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	2	
(NH ₄) ₂ 6MO ₇ O ₂₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.9	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	2	
<i>Vitamin solution</i>		1 mL
Thiamine	10	
Cyanocobalamin	10	
Biotin	0.2	

A.14. Zarrouk medium

Zarrouk medium components and concentrations ^{266,297}

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity used for medium
NaNO ₃		2.5 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		0.5 g
K ₂ SO ₄		1 g
NaCl		1 g
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.2 g
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O		0.04 g
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O		0.01 g
EDTA		0.08 g
NaHCO ₃		16.8 g
<i>Micronutrient solution</i>		1 mL
H ₃ BO ₃	2.86	
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.81	
ZnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.222	
Na ₂ MoO ₄	0.0177	
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.079	

A.15. Modified K medium

Modified K medium for the growth of marine dinoflagellates ²⁰²

Component	Quantity for 10 mL medium
NaNO ₃	0.075 g
NH ₄ Cl	0.00268 g
NaH ₂ PO ₄	0.0012 g
TRIS	0.121 g
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	0.034 g
Fe-Na-EDTA	0.00542 g
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.00018 g
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.0000230 g
CoSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.0000125 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.00000726 g
H ₂ SeO ₃	0.00000129 g
Thiamine	0.000186 g
Biotin	0.000000512 g
B12	0.000000501 g

Note: Filter-sterilized Mediterranean seawater was used to prepare the medium.

A.16. ES-DK medium

ES-DK medium ²⁹⁸

Component	Quantity for 1 L medium
NaNO ₃	32.55 mg
Glycerophosphate of Na	4.65 mg
<i>Trace Metals</i>	
Na ₂ EDTA (2 sources)	3.860 mg
Fe(NH ₄) ₂ (SO ₄) ₂ ·6H ₂ O	1.632 mg
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	0.114 mg
H ₃ BO ₃	2.651 mg
MnSO ₄	0.286 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.051 mg
CoSO ₄ ·(x)H ₂ O	0.011 mg
<i>Vitamins</i>	
Thiamine·HCl	0.1 mg
Biotin	0.5 µg
B ₁₂	0.5 µg
<i>Seawater</i>	1 L

Note: In Lim's ²³⁷ algaeculture, seawater (33 psu salinity) from Okkirai Bay was used as the medium base. Medium salinity was adjusted to 15 psu by dilution with deionized distilled water. The pH of culture medium was adjusted to 7.8–7.9.

A.17. GSe medium (modified GPM medium)

GSe Medium for the growth of marine dinoflagellates²³⁹

Component	Stock solution mg per 1L dH ₂ O	Quantity for 1 L medium
Seawater		750 mL
Glass-distilled water		204 mL
KNO ₃		0.2 g
K ₂ HPO ₄		0.035 g
<i>Soil extract</i>		15 mL
<i>P_{II} metals (pH adjusted to 7.5)</i>		30 mL
EDTA (Na, H ₂ O) ₂	1.27	
H ₃ BO ₃ _{1.14}		
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	0.0484	
MnCl ₂ ·4 H ₂ O	0.144	
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.004	
ZnCl ₂	0.0104	
Vitamin B ₁₂		1 μg
Thiamin·HCl		1 mg
Biotin		2 μg
H ₂ SeO ₃		0.0322 mg

The **soil extract** was made by autoclaving at 15 psi for 15 min equal weights of unfertilized loamy soil and glass distilled water, filtering through Whatman No. 1 filter paper, and reautoclaving.

A.18. L1 basal culture medium

L1 Basal Culture Medium ²⁴³

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O
NaNO ₃	0.25 g
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.019 g
NaSiO ₃ ·9H ₂ O	0.1 g
<i>Trace elements</i>	
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	0.015 g
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	0.011 g
MnCl ₂ ·H ₂ O	0.44 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.08 mg
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.03 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	8.32 µg
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.07 mg
H ₂ SeO ₃	4.30 µg
NiSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	8.77 µg
Na ₃ VO ₄	6.13 µg
K ₂ CrO ₄	6.47 µg
<i>Vitamins</i>	
Cyanocobalamin	1.67 µg
Biotin	1.67 µg
Thiamine HCl	0.33 mg

A.19. ESAW H1 medium

ESAW H1 Medium ²⁴⁴

Component	Stock solution (g per 1L dH ₂ O)
(1) Salt solution – <i>anhydrous slats</i> ^a	
NaCl	21.19 g
Na ₂ SO ₄	3.55 g
KCl	0.599 g
NaHCO ₃	0.174 g
KBr	0.0863 g
H ₃ BO ₃ ^b	0.0230 g
NaF	0.0028 g
(2) Salt solution – <i>hydrated slats</i> ^a	
MgCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	9.592 g
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1.344 g
SrCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.0218g
(3) HEPES	0.238 g
(4) Major nutrient I - <i>nitrate</i> [1 mL·L ⁻¹]	46.7 g
NaNO ₃	
(5) Major nutrient II - <i>phosphate</i> [1 mL·L ⁻¹]	
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O ^c	3.09 g
(6) Major nutrient III - <i>silicate</i> [2 mL·L ⁻¹]	
Na ₂ SiO ₃ ·9H ₂ O ^d	15 g
(7) Metal stock I - <i>iron</i> [1 mL·L ⁻¹]	
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O ^e	1.77 g
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	3.09 g
(8) Metal stock II - <i>trace metals</i> [1 mL·L ⁻¹] ^f	
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.073 g
CoSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.016 g
MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	0.54 g
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O ^g	1.48 × 10 ³ g
Na ₂ SeO ₃	1.73 × 10 ⁴ g
NiCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	1.49 × 10 ³ g
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	2.44 g
(9) Vitamin stock [1 mL·L ⁻¹] ^h	
Thiamine HCl	0.1 g
Biotin	0.002 g
B ₁₂	0.001 g

^a Anyhydrous and hydrated salts must be dissolved separately; masses assume specific gravity = 1.021 at 20 °C.

^b Borate now added only in salt solution, not in trace metals.

^c New phosphate source removes the organic glycerophosphate.

^d Silicate stock solution is not acidified and is made at half previous strength to facilitate dissolution.

^e Iron now added solely as chloride (removes ammonium) in a separate stock with equimolar EDTA.

^f Trace metal stock now made 10× original concentration. EDTA must be dissolved first. For convenience, each metal can be added at 10 mL/L from individual 100× concentrated stocks.

^g New addition to recipe.

^h Filter sterilize; store frozen.

A.20. L1 medium

L1 Medium ²⁴⁶ Marine dinoflagellates

Stocks

- (1) NaNO₃ per liter
75 g
 (2) NaH₂PO₄·2H₂O 5.65 g
 (3) Trace elements: There are 11 chemicals. Prepare Primary stock solutions first. Add first two chemicals separately in **500ml/dH₂O**, allowing each to completely dissolve before adding the primary stocks in order:

Component	Primary stock solutions	Amount/Volume for 500ml working stock solution
	10ml dH ₂ O	
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	-	2.18 g
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	-	1.575 g
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.0245 g	0.125 mL
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.199 g	1.5 mL
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.22 g	0.5 mL
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.1 g	0.5 mL
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	1.8 g	0.5 mL
H ₂ SeO ₃	0.026 g	0.5 mL
NiSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	0.027 g	0.5 mL
Na ₃ VO ₄	0.0184 g	0.5 mL
K ₂ CrO ₄	0.0194 g	0.5 mL

(4) Vitamin mix:

- Cyanocobalamin (Vitamin B₁₂) per liter
0.0005 g
 Biotin 0.0005 g
 Thiamine HCl (Vitamin B₁) 0.1 g

A.21. Daigo's IMK medium

Daigo's IMK Medium ²²³

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O
NaNO ₃	200 mg
NaH ₂ PO ₄	1.4 mg
KH ₂ PO ₄	5 mg
NH ₄ Cl	2.68 mg
Fe-EDTA	5.2 mg
Mn-EDTA	0.332 mg
Na ₂ -EDTA	37.2 mg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.023 mg
CoSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	0.014 mg
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	0.0073 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	0.0025 mg
H ₂ SeO ₃	0.0017 mg
Thiamine-HCl	0.2 mg
Biotin	0.0015 mg
Vitamin B12	0.0015 mg

A.22. LDM medium

LDM Medium ²⁹⁹

Component	Primary stock solutions 100 mL dH ₂ O	per liter
<i>pasteurized, filtered seawater</i>		892 mL
tryptone		1 g
bristol's solution (<i>see recipe below</i>)		100 mL
PIV metal solution (<i>see recipe below</i>)		6 mL
<i>Vitamins</i>		
biotin	25.0 µg	1 mL
vitamin B ₁₂	15.0 µg	1 mL

Preparation of Bristol's Solution

Component	Primary stock solutions 400ml dH ₂ O	per liter
<i>glass-distilled water</i>		940 mL
NaNO ₃	10.0	10 mL
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	1.0	10 mL
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	3.0	10 mL
K ₂ HPO ₄	3.0	10 mL
KH ₂ PO ₄	7.0	10 mL
NaCl	1.0	10 mL

Preparation of PIV Metal Solution

Component	per liter
<i>glass-distilled water</i>	1000 mL
Na ₂ EDTA	0.750 g

A.23. A+ medium

A+ Medium ²⁸⁵

Component	Stock solution g per 1L dH ₂ O
NaCl	18.0
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	5.0
urea	0.6
Tris-HCl (pH 8.2)	0.998
KCl	0.596
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.325
KH ₂ PO ₄	0.0499
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	0.0299
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	3.89 mg
NiSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	0.263 mg
cyanocobalamin (B ₁₂)	4.0 µg
<i>Trace metals</i>	
H ₂ BO ₃	0.0338
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	4.32 mg
ZnCl ₂	0.313 mg
MoO ₃ (85%)	0.0266 mg
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	0.0106 mg
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	2.99 µg

A.24. F/2-RSE medium

F/2-RSE Medium ²⁵⁵

Component	Stock solution mg per 1L dH ₂ O
ReefSalt (H2Ocean, Pro+, UK)	4 g
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	5.65
NaNO ₃	100
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	4.16
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	3.15
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	9.8 µg
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	22 µg
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	10 µg
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	0.18
Na ₂ Mo ₄ ·2H ₂ O	6.3 µg
Thiamine-HCl	0.1
Vitamin B ₁₂	0.5 µg
Biotin	0.5 µg

A.25. Modified brody emerson nutrient medium

Modified Brody Emerson Nutrient Medium ³⁰⁰

Component	Stock solution mg per 1L dH ₂ O
KNO ₃	826
NaNO ₃	250
CaCl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	0.83
KH ₂ PO ₄	58.3
K ₂ HPO ₄	413.3
MgSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1692
KCl	5333
NaCl	6260
KI	333
KBr	333
ME	0.51
Ca(NO ₃) ₂	113
Soil (soil extract)	10000
EDTA	33
FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1.66
H ₃ BO ₃	4.83
% salinity	0.6
<i>Trace elements</i>	
H ₃ BO ₃	7.76
MnSO ₄ ·4H ₂ O	1.52
CoSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	1/17
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	1.62
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	5.36
NH ₄ Mo ₇ O ₂₄	1.59

Appendix 2. Culture collections

Acronym	Name	Link
AC	Algobank-Caen Université de Caen Normandie <i>France</i>	Click here
BEA	Spaniard Algae Bank (Banco Español de Algas) <i>Spain</i>	Click here
CCAP	Culture Collection of Algae and Protozoa at Scottish Association for Marine Science <i>UK</i>	Click here
CPCC	Canadian Phycological Culture Centre Canada <i>Formerly known as the University of Toronto Culture Collection (UTCC) of Algae and Cyanobacteria</i>	Click here
CSMA	Culture Collection of the Centro di Studio dei Microrganismi Autotrofi <i>Italy</i>	n/a
IBVF	Biological Culture Service of the Institute of Plant Biochemistry and Photosynthesis <i>Spain</i>	Click here
LEGE-CC	Blue Biotechnology and Ecotoxicology Culture Collection at CIIMAR <i>Portugal</i>	Click here
NCMA <i>Formerly CCMP</i>	National Center for Marine Algae and Microbiota at Bigelow Laboratory <i>USA</i> <i>Formerly known as the Culture Collection of Marine Phytoplankton (CCMP)</i>	Click here
NIES	National Institute for Environmental Studies <i>Japan</i>	Click here
PCC	Pasteur Culture Collection of Cyanobacteria <i>France</i>	Click here
RCC	Roscoff Culture Collection <i>France</i>	Click here
SAG	Sammlung von Algenkulturen der Universität Göttingen / Culture Collection of Algae at Göttingen University <i>Germany</i>	Click here
SCCAP	Scandinavian Culture Collection of Algae & Protozoa at The University of Copenhagen <i>Denmark</i>	Click here
UTEX	Culture Collection of Algae at The University of Texas at Austin <i>USA</i>	Click here

Appendix 3. List of images

Chlorophyta

1. *Ankistrodesmus falcatus*³⁰¹
(Chlorophyceae)

2. *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*³⁰³
(Chlorophyceae)

3. *Chromochloris zofingiensis*³⁰⁵
(Chlorophyceae)

4. *Desmodesmus subspicatus*³⁰⁷
(Chlorophyceae)

5. *Dunaliella salina*³⁰⁸
(Chlorophyceae)

6. *Dunaliella tertiolecta*³¹⁰
(Chlorophyceae)

7. *Graesiella* sp.³¹²
(Chlorophyceae)

8. *Haematococcus pluvialis*³¹⁴
(Chlorophyceae)

9. *Scenedesmus obliquus*³¹⁶
(Chlorophyceae)

10. *Scenedesmus quadricauda*³⁰²
(Chlorophyceae)

11. *Selenastrum capricornutum*³⁰⁴
(Chlorophyceae)

12. *Auxenochlorella protothecoides*³⁰⁶
(Trebouxiophyceae)

13. *Botryococcus braunii*²⁷⁴
(Trebouxiophyceae)

14. *Chlorella sorokiniana*³⁰⁹
(Trebouxiophyceae)

15. *Chlorella vulgaris*³¹¹
(Trebouxiophyceae)

16. *Jaagichlorella luteoviridis*³¹³
(Trebouxiophyceae)

17. *Parachlorella kessleri*³¹⁵
(Trebouxiophyceae)

18. *Picochlorum* sp.
(Trebouxiophyceae)

19. *Tetraselmis subcordiformis*³¹⁷
(Chlorodendrophyceae)

20. *Tetraselmis suecica*³¹⁸
(Chlorodendrophyceae)

Bacillariophyta

21. *Chaetoceros calcitrans*³¹⁹
(Mediophyceae)

25. *Thalassiosira pseudonana*³²⁰
(Mediophyceae)

22. *Cyclotella* sp.³²¹
(Mediophyceae)

26. *Navicula* sp.³²²
(Bacillariophyceae)

23. *Odontella aurita*³²³
(Mediophyceae)

27. *Nitzschia* sp.³²⁴
(Bacillariophyceae)

24. *Skeletonema* sp.³²⁵
(Mediophyceae)

28. *Phaeodactylum tricornerum*³²⁶
(Bacillariophyceae)

Ochrophyta

29. *Ochromonas* sp.³²⁷
(Chrysophyceae)

31. *Nannochloropsis oculata*³²⁸
(Eustigmatophyceae)

30. *Microchloropsis salina*³²⁹
(Eustigmatophyceae)

Euglenophyta

32. *Euglena gracilis*³³⁰
(Euglenophyceae)

Cryptophyta

33. *Rhodomonas* sp. ³³¹
(Cryptophyceae)

Haptophyta

34. *Isochrysis galbana* ³³²
(Coccolithophyceae)

35. *Tisochrysis lutea* ³³³
(Coccolithophyceae)

36. *Pavlova* sp. ²²³
(Pavlovophyceae)

Dinophyta

37. *Amphidinium carterae* ³³⁴
(Dinophyceae)

38. *Alexandrium minutum* ³²³
(Dinophyceae)

39. *Chaetoceros calcitrans* ³¹⁹
(Dinophyceae)

40. *Karlodinium veneficum* ³³⁵
(Dinophyceae)

Rhodophyta

41. *Galdieria sulphuraria* ³³⁶
(Cyanidiophyceae)

42. *Porphyridium purpureum* ³³⁸
(Porphyridiophyceae)

43. *Rhodella* sp. ³³⁷
(Rhodellophyceae)

Cyanobacteria

44. *Anabaena cylindrica* ³³⁹
(Cyanophyceae)

45. *Arthrospira platensis* ³⁴¹
(Cyanophyceae)

46. *Lyngbya lutea* ³⁴³
(Cyanophyceae)

47. *Microcystis aeruginosa* ³⁴⁵
(Cyanophyceae)

48. *Nostoc* sp. ³⁴⁰
(Cyanophyceae)

49. *Synechococcus* sp. ³⁴²
(Cyanophyceae)

50. *Synechocystis* sp. ³⁴⁴
(Cyanophyceae)

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